

האוניברסיטה העברית בירושלים
THE HEBREW UNIVERSITY OF JERUSALEM
الجامعة العبرية في اورشليم القدس

Valency Classes and Alternations in Persian

Asael Benyami

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment
of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Arts

Carried out under the supervision of
Alena Witzlack-Makarevich and Pegah Faghiri

Department of Linguistics
Faculty of Humanities
The Hebrew University of Jerusalem

December 2022

© 2022

Asael Benyami

Asael.Benyami@mail.huji.ac.il

Abstract

This thesis presents a detailed study of valency classes and alternation in Persian, a South-Western Iranian language with more than 110 million speakers worldwide, mostly in Iran. It contributes to a better understanding and description of the Persian verbal system and thereby also to the development of cross-linguistic research on argument structure and valency alternations.

For this purpose, a total of 94 verbs were analyzed and described for their valency coding frames and alternations, following the methodological steps developed by the *Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes* (Malchukov & team 2015). These coding frames were then grouped into ten different valency classes based on the number and nature of their arguments. With respect to valency alternations, this thesis presents two types of coded alternations, namely the passive and the causative, and three types of uncoded alternations, namely =*rā* alternations, *ezāfe* alternations, and other prepositional alternations.

In addition to the typological contribution this thesis presents, inspired by the other languages documented in the online database *Valency Patterns Leipzig (ValPaL)* (Hartmann et al. 2013), the list of predicates investigated in this thesis can be useful for language teaching, lexicography, or other database purposes, databases such as *PersPred* (Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a).

Keywords: valency, valency alternation, Persian language, *ezāfe*, complex predicates, *rā*, Iranian linguistics.

תקציר העבודה - Hebrew Abstract

תיזה זו מציגה מחקר אמפרי מפורט על אודות דגמי הערכיות והחילופים (אלטרנציות) שלהן בפרסית, שפה איראנית דרום-מערבית, שלה מעל ל-110 מיליון דוברים בעולם, רובם באיראן. העבודה מרימה תרומה להבנה ולתיאור של מערכת הפועל הפרסית, ומתוך כך גם לפיתוח המחקר הטיפולוגי חוצה-הלשונית על מבנה ארגומנטים וחילופי ערכיות.

לשם כך, דגמי הערכיות של 94 פעלים נאספו, נותחו ותוארו, בהתבסס על שיטות העבודה המוצעות בשאלון לדגמי ערכיות של אוניברסיטת לייפציג (*Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes*) (Malchukov & team 2015). בהמשך, דגמי הערכיות חולקו לעשר קבוצות ערכיות (*va-lency classes*) על פי מספר הארגומנטים ואופיים. באשר לחילופי ערכיות, תיזה זו מציגה שני סוגים של חילופים שמסומנים על הפועל (*coded alternations*), והם הסביל והגרימה, וכן שלושה סוגים של חילופים שאינם מסומנים על הפועל (*uncoded alternations*), והם חילופי $=rā$, חילופי *ezāfe*, וחילופים אחרים באמצעות מילות יחס תחיליות.

בנוסף לתרומה הטיפולוגית של תיזה זו, שנערכה בהשראת תיאורי שפות נוספות במסד הנתונים האינטרנטי של דגמי ערכיות של אוניברסיטת לייפציג (*ValPaL*) (Hartmann et al. 2013), רשימת הפרדיקטים שנחקרו ונותחו יכולה להועיל לתחומים נוספים כמו הוראת שפות, מילונאות, או עיבוי מסדי נתונים אחרים לשפה הפרסית, כדוגמת *PersPred* (Samvelian & Faghiri 2013b).

מילות מפתח: ערכיות, חילופי ערכיות, אלטרנציות, השפה הפרסית, אצ'אפה, פעלים מורכבים, בלשנות איראנית.

Acknowledgements

This thesis could not have come to fruition without the help and support of numerous people, and I wish to extend my gratitude to all of them.

First of all, I would like to acknowledge my supervisors, Dr. Alena Witzlack-Makarevich from HUJI and Dr. Pegah Faghiri from UvA. Alena guided me in every stage of this study, directing me to stay on the right track and not give up (in her kind words: “Don’t get stuck!”). Her instructive and insightful comments and suggestions taught me tremendously and I am truly grateful for having the opportunity to learn from her.

I am also extremely grateful for the time and effort that Pegah put into helping me through this thesis. Pegah is an academic inspiration, her research on Persian syntax, especially on complex predicates, has influenced and benefited this thesis in many ways.

Many thanks to my colleagues and friends for their continuous encouragement and support, especially to Shirli Simani for keeping up with my constant nagging about the Persian language; to Eliana K. Kessler for her ever so precious comments and insights on this work; and to Zohar Figlash for offering a cup of tea or coffee when I truly needed one.

I also wish to thank my family for their support along the way, and to my best friends, Liat Mor, Osnat Shineberg, and Ido Halpern-Glikman, who were there in times of need and warmed my heart with their love.

Lastly, this thesis is dedicated to the memory of my dear friend, Assaf Shomer. His kind friendship and thoughtful advice are truly missed, may he rest in peace.

Contents

Abstract	i
Hebrew Abstract - תקציר העבודה	ii
Acknowledgements	iii
Abbreviations	vi
List of Tables and Figures	vii
1 Introduction	1
2 Terminology and foundations	2
2.1 Valency	2
2.2 Arguments vs. adjuncts	5
2.3 Transitivity	7
3 The Persian language	10
3.1 General remarks and state of study	10
3.2 Basic morphosyntax	12
3.2.1 Clause structure	12
3.2.2 Noun phrase and pronouns	13
3.2.3 <i>Ezāfe</i>	14
3.2.4 Adpositions	15
3.2.4.1 Omission of adpositions	16
3.2.4.2 The postposition = <i>rā</i>	16
3.2.5 Persian verbal system	19
3.2.6 Complex predicates	20
4 Date and methods	23
4.1 Corpora	23
4.2 The Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes	25
5 Valency classes in Persian	28
5.1 Aivalent predicates: coding frame <(NVE) V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>	28
5.2 Monovalent predicates	28
5.2.1 Intransitive: coding frame <1 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	28
5.2.2 Intransitive: coding frame <(1) NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>	29
5.3 Bivalent predicates	30
5.3.1 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+rā (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	30
5.3.2 Intransitive: coding frame <1 PP+2 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	30
5.3.3 Intransitive: coding frame <(1) PP+2 NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>	31
5.3.4 Intransitive: coding frame <1 NVE=EZ+2 V.SUBJ[1]>	32
5.4 Trivalent predicates	32
5.4.1 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+rā PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	32
5.4.2 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+rā 3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	33
5.4.3 Intransitive: coding frame <1 PP+2 PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>	34

6	Valency alternations in Persian	36
6.1	Coded alternations	36
6.1.1	Passive	36
6.1.2	Causative	37
6.2	Uncoded alternations	38
6.2.1	= <i>rā</i> alternations	39
6.2.1.1	= <i>rā</i> and <i>be</i> 'to' alternation: Dative alternation	39
6.2.1.2	= <i>rā</i> and <i>bā</i> 'with' alternation: Reciprocal alternation	40
6.2.1.3	= <i>rā</i> and LOC alternation: Locative alternation	40
6.2.2	<i>Ezāfe</i> alternations	40
6.2.3	Other prepositional alternations	42
7	Discussion	44
8	Conclusion	48
	Appendix	58
	References	58

Abbreviations

1	first person
2	second person
3	third person
COP	copula
CPr	complex predicate
DFLT	default
DIM	diminutive
DOM	differential object marking
EZ	<i>ezāfe</i>
IMP	imperative
INDF	indefinite
INTR	intransitive
IPFV	imperfective
LV	light verb (of a complex predicate)
NEG	negative
NVE	non-verbal element (of a complex predicate)
PRON	pronoun
PRF	perfect
PTCP	participle
PL	plural
PRS	present tense
PREV	preverb
PST	past tense
RSTR	restrictive relative
SG	singular
SUBJ	subject
SBJV	subjunctive
TR	transitive
UTT	utterance

List of Tables

1	Pronominal paradigm	13
2	Persian infinitives and stems	19
3	Valency classes divided by transitivity	44
4	Transliteration	50
5	Valency classes and alternations summary	51

List of Figures

1	A geographic overview of the Iranian language family	10
2	CQL search for <i>ḥarf zadan</i> ‘to talk’ with the preposition <i>az</i> ‘about’ (lit. ‘from’)	24
3	Examples of <i>ḥarf zadan</i> ‘to talk’ with the preposition <i>az</i> ‘about’ (lit. ‘from’)	24
4	CQL search for <i>ḥarf zadan</i> ‘to talk’ with the <i>ezāfe</i> argument (+ = <i>rā</i>)	25
5	Examples of <i>ḥarf zadan</i> ‘to talk’ with the <i>ezāfe</i> argument (+ = <i>rā</i>)	25

1 Introduction

This thesis is an empirical study of the main valency patterns and valency alternations in Persian. *Valency* usually refers to the number and nature of *arguments*, i.e., core participants, a verb requires in order to convey a complete meaning in a clause. The different verbs in a language that display similar valencies can be coded and grouped into *valency classes* based on their *valency frames*, i.e., individual argument(s) marking patterns. When a single verb (one verb lemma) productively displays more than one valency frame, this is called a *valency alternation*. These alternations may be *coded*, i.e., marked (usually morphologically) on the verb, or *uncoded*, i.e., no change occurs on the verb.

This thesis has two primary goals: the first is to contribute to a better understanding and description of the Persian verbal system and thereby to improve our knowledge of its different predicates and their argument structure properties; the second is to contribute to a cross-linguistic typological understanding of verbs in general and how different languages use and mark them.

For the purpose of achieving a typologically comparable description of the Persian verbal system, I followed the methodology developed by the *Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes* (Malchukov & team 2015), which established a set of 70 core verb meanings (upon which I added 17 additional verb meanings). Based on these 87 core verb meanings, 94 predicates were described and grouped into ten valency classes according to the different valency patterns they exhibit: one aivalent, two monovalent, four bivalent, and three trivalent. Following this classification, two coded alternations were described, namely the passive and the causative, as well as three types of uncoded alternations, namely *=rā* alternations, *ezāfe* alternations, and other prepositional alternations.

The remainder of this thesis is outlined as follows: Section 2 introduces the general terminology and notions used in this thesis with regards to the study of valency; Section 3 contains information concerning the Persian language in general and the relevant basic morphosyntactic features of the language; Section 4 explains the data and methods used in this thesis; Section 5 shows the different valency classes divided by number of arguments; Section 6 presents the different valency alternations found, divided into coded and uncoded alternations; Section 7 discusses some of the different valency classes and alternations and raises several issues concerning their syntactic behavior, and Section 8 provides concluding remarks and suggestions for future research.

2 Terminology and foundations

We have many names and different understandings to the things we love. In order to avoid confusion, I present the terms and notions used in this thesis below.

2.1 Valency

The term *valency* (also known as *valence*)¹ refers to a special type of dependency property exhibited by different lexical items. As Allerton defines it, “[It] involves a relationship between, on the one hand, the different subclasses of a word class (such as verb) and, on the other, the different structural environments required by those subclasses, these environments varying both in the number and in the types of element” (Allerton 2006: 301). In other words, members of a word class (such as verbs or nouns) can be grouped into subclasses based on the syntactic properties they display within a clause, viz. their interaction with other required (perhaps even allowed) elements in the sentence.

In the case of a verb, valency generally refers to the number and nature of *arguments* (in contrast to *adjuncts*) a verb requires (see also Section 2.2 below). Essentially, despite the differences in the meanings of individual verbs within a given language, many verbs display similar valency in terms of their morpho-syntactic behavior by e.g., requiring the same number of arguments and/or coding their arguments in the same manner. For individual argument(s) marking patterns, the term *valency frame* (or *valency pattern*) is usually used. According to their valency frame, verbs in a given language may usually be grouped into a discrete number of *valency classes*. These syntactic verb classes often correlate with semantic classes (Comrie et al. 2015a: 3).

The valency of a verb may also alternate via various syntactic and/or morphological operations. One differentiates between *coded valency alternations*, where the verb undergoes a change (e.g., the English Passive alternation), and *uncoded valency alternations*, where the form of the verb is the same with the two alternate valency frames (e.g., the English dative alternation) (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 65). While some alternations do not affect the number of arguments, others increase or reduce them, e.g., in (1b), the Turkish causative morpheme *-dUr* has been added to the verb, which has increased the valency of the predicate by one and produced a two-argument clause. The introduced causer (*Ali*) appears as the new subject (marked in NOM) whereas the base subject (*Hasan*) is now

¹The term itself originates in the scientific study of chemistry, in which the valency of a chemical element is its capacity to combine with a fixed number of atoms of another element.

a direct object (marked in ACC).

(1) Turkish

- a. *Hasan öl-dü.*
Hasan[NOM] die-PST
'Hasan died.' (Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019: 16)²
- b. *Ali Hasan-ı öl-dür-dü.*
Ali[NOM] Hassan-ACC die-CAUS-PST
'Ali killed Hasan.' (Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019: 16)

There is an extensive amount of literature on valency that stems from different linguistic approaches. The invention of the notion of 'valency' is usually credited to Tesnière (1959), who emphasized the distinction between arguments (*actants*) and adjuncts (*circonstants*). In his study, Tesnière argues that the verb is the 'central node' (*noeud des noeuds*) of the clause, and it achieves this central role through its high position in the hierarchy of connections but also through its ability to determine the number and variety of its dependents (*subordonnés*) (Allerton 2006: 302). In Tesnière's approach, alongside scholars such as Helbig & Schenkel (1969),³ verbal valency classes are defined more in terms of formal rather than semantic criteria. These types of contributions were influential to the study of Dependency Grammar in the late 1950s and throughout 1960s.

In the 1970s, building up on Tesnière approach, research on valency classes developed with the study of Case Grammar. Studies by scholars such as Chafe (1970), Fillmore (1970, 1977), Anderson (1971, 1977), and Jackendoff (1976), identified verb classes in terms of the semantic roles of the verbal arguments. Nevertheless, most of these types of research, if not all, have dealt almost exclusively with European languages. In the decades that followed, the argument structure of verb classes has played a major part in different linguistic theories.

In the generative tradition, the issue of subcategorization frames of different verb classes based on their argument structure has been prevalent for a long time, but has rarely been carried out systematically. One outstanding study in this regard is Levin (1993), on English verb classes and alternations. In her study, similar to Apresjan (1969) on Russian verbs, Levin presents a fine-grained classification of English verb classes based both

²Glossing follows the Leipzig Glossing Rules (Comrie et al. 2015b) with some additions (see Abbreviations). I took the liberty to standardize the original abbreviations in examples reproduced from other sources and, if necessary, to modify the glosses in accordance with the Leipzig Glossing Rules. References to examples are given after the translation in round brackets if taken from academic literature or square brackets if taken from corpora/elicited. see Section 4.1 for more information about the corpora used in this thesis.

³See Ágel (2006) for a more comprehensive bibliography of valency research.

on their lexical-semantic and syntactic properties. Unlike previous studies in which the verbal lexicon was divided only into a few very general classes (e.g., active vs. stative verbs, transitive vs intransitive, unaccusatives and unergatives, etc.), Levin (1993) defines verb classes systematically by their overall syntactic distributions and properties. These include not only the verb argument structure, but also the possible argument structure alternations, as well as different syntactic diagnostics (e.g., middle alternation, unspecified object deletion, *there*-insertion, etc.). This study (alongside later publications, e.g., Levin & Hovav Rappaport 2005) has laid the groundwork for many other theoretical works across different linguistic disciplines.

Nevertheless, because the verb classes of Levin (1993) are constructed based on syntactic criteria, they pose an issue regarding typological research. Since Levin's verb classes are not always semantically coherent, trying to decide which aspects of her classification are universals and which are language-specific may be impossible. The same is true for the encoding of alternative constructions, as well as the syntactic diagnostics, e.g., English middle alternation (Comrie et al. 2015a: 4).

In the 1990s and early 2000s, research on verb classes and valency has experienced growth in typological studies. Studies by Lehmann (1991), Drossard (1991), Lazard (1998), Dixon (1991, 2005), among others, albeit based on previous valency related linguistic traditions, are typological in nature. For example, Dixon's taxonomy of verb classes focuses on the semantic nature of the verb, whereas its syntactic properties are secondary. Even though Dixon's research is on English verbs, it can be more easily extended to the study of other languages. One exceptional contribution in this regard is research done by Tsunoda (1981, 1985), who proposed a hierarchy (or a *semantic map*) of verb types that predicts the distribution of intransitive and transitive patterns in individual languages.

In more recent years, contributions that continue this type of cross-linguistic research include studies by Malchukov (2005, 2006, 2016), Malchukov et al. (2010), Kratochvíl et al. (2011), Croft (2012), De Clerck et al. (2013), Hellan et al. (2017), Grossman & Witzlack-Makarevich (2019), among others. The state of the art attempt to offer a comprehensive typology of valency classes is the *Leipzig Valency Classes Project* (Malchukov & Comrie 2015a,b), which carried out a large-scale cross-linguistic comparison of valency classes.

Inspired by Levin (1993) and a direct continuation of Malchukov et al.'s (2010) research on ditransitive constructions in the languages of the world, the project has set to typologically investigate the argument-structure properties of verbs of different valency classes.

More broadly, the project focused on uncovering the variability of valency-based verb classification across languages and to explore to what extent this variability depends on (or can be derived from) variation in grammatical constructions found in individual languages (Hartmann et al. 2013).

Building on the previously mentioned approaches and traditions, the project's objectives are bottom-up taxonomic in nature, as in Levin's (1993) approach, semantically based in a way that can be applied to other languages cross-linguistically, similar to Lehmann (1991) and Dixon (1991, 2005), and assist the overall research of valency by going a step further in uncovering universal and language-specific coding properties and behaviors of valency classes, like Tsunoda's (1981, 1985) semantic maps (Comrie et al. 2015a: 7).

There are two major outcomes of the project: two edited volumes by Andrej Malchukov and Bernard Comrie (2015a, 2015b) called *Valency Classes in the World's Languages* and the online database *Valency Patterns Leipzig*, also known as *ValPaL* (Hartmann et al. 2013). The edited volumes contain 30 chapters by an international team of researchers addressing the topic of valency classes and valency alternations in different, structurally and genealogically diverse languages, as well as general chapters written by the project members and other experts in the field. The database, which does not adhere to the same space limitations as the edited volumes, acts as an online interface that allows its users, among other things, to look at specific valency coding frames across languages.

2.2 Arguments vs. adjuncts

Since at least Tesnière (1959), it has been widely accepted that there is a distinction between arguments and adjuncts (Tesnière's 'actants' and 'circonstants'). This distinction is often regarded as crucial to many linguistic frameworks, especially to the study of valency where it is integral to its definition (see Haspelmath 2014 and Witzlack-Makarevich 2019: 5-7 for recent overviews).

The intuitive distinction is straightforward and easy to understand: arguments are an inherent part of the valency of a verb, essential to complete the sense of a predicate, whereas adjuncts, which give less essential information, are not. However, difficulties emerge as soon as one tries to distinguish the two in specific cases and cross-linguistically.

One way to distinguish between the two is by considering the verb's meaning: if a participant is entailed by the meaning of a verb, this participant is an argument, otherwise it is an adjunct (e.g., Bickel 2011). Consider the bracketed phrases in (2).

- (2) a. *They cut the apples [with the knife].*
b. *He broke the window [with a rock].*

According to the entailment-based definition, the bracketed phrase in (2a) would be an argument, since *cut* means ‘sever with a sharp instrument’. On the other hand, the bracketed phrase in (2b) would not be an argument, because *break* only means ‘do something so that something becomes broken’. Nonetheless, not all entailed participants can be overtly expressed, not all entailed participants would be considered arguments, and not all elements that are generally considered arguments are entailed participants (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 46).

Therefore, this type of argument definition was not adopted for the *Leipzig Valency Classes Project* (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 47), and hence for this thesis as well. Instead, the authors consider the notion of *verb-specificity* as the most suitable way to capture the argument-adjunct distinction: arguments are verb-specific dependent elements in a clause, which are most notably identifiable by their *coding properties*, i.e., *flagging* (case or adpositional marking) and/or *indexing* (traditionally called *agreement*, i.e., bound person marking associated with the verb). In contrast, adjuncts are verb-independent (or not verb-specific) elements in a clause, which provide supplementary or circumstantial information, such as locational, temporal, illocutionary or manner setting adverbials (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 42). For example, the verbs in (3) are very similar, or even identical in meaning, but are different in the way they flag their arguments.

- (3) a. *I was expecting **you** [today].*
b. *I was waiting **for you** [today].*

In both (3a) and (3b) examples, the bracketed participant *today* is not flagged and would be considered an adjunct which denotes a temporal setting, whereas the boldfaced participant *you* would be considered an argument, since it is a verb-specific participant needed to complete the predicate. However, even though the semantic role of *you* is not very (if at all) different in (3a) and (3b), it is flagged differently in each example: only the verb in example (3b) requires the preposition *for*. This idiosyncratic coding property is not predictable and needs to be learned in addition to the meaning of the verb itself (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 47).

Besides specific coding properties, another crucial criterion for (non-)argumenthood

is *specificity of occurrence*, defined by Haspelmath & Hartmann as “whether a nominal is limited in its cooccurrence options to a restricted and semantically arbitrary set of verbs (i.e., whether it is verb-specific), or whether it can occur with any verb, or at least with a large and semantically coherent class of verbs (i.e., whether it is verb-free)” (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 49). This criterion can often be reflected using the widely cited test known as the *do so* test (e.g., see Haspelmath 2014 for examples from different languages): if a clause can be paraphrased in such a way that a constituent from the original clause is removed and occurs in an anaphoric *do so* (or *happen*) clause, then this constituent is an adjunct (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 49):

- (4) a. *She called her mother, and did so in the morning.*
b. **She called, and did so her mother.*
c. ?*They cut the apples, and did so with the knife.*

In (4a), *did so* is used for *calling her mother*, thus *in the morning* is an adjunct. In (4b), *did so* cannot be used only for *calling*, thus *her mother* is an argument. In (4c), however, the result of the test is not so clear.

Other tests to diagnose argumenthood exist, but are known to suffer from a number of shortcomings (for discussion, see Comrie 1993). In practice, it is often the case that both syntactic and semantic criteria are applied to determine between arguments and adjuncts, and in any case, these appear to be language-particular descriptive linguistics categories (Haspelmath 2014: 1).

Thus, the *ValPaL* database is not consistent in the distinction between arguments and adjuncts, and every contributor made their own decisions. The editors argue that distinguishing consistently between arguments and adjuncts across languages is not really necessary to capture the most important aspects of valency variation. As in other areas of morpho-syntax, comparison of verbal valency is based on comparative semantic concepts (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 68).

2.3 Transitivity

Transitivity, which is important to practically every linguistic theory, is often thought to be a universal phenomena. Although various definitions have been proposed from different perspectives, the term is often used in a way that assumes its meaning without any attempt at a precise definition (Næss 2007: 2).

According to traditional grammar, transitivity is a property of a verb or an entire clause, referring to a particular valency pattern that involves two obligatory participants: the direct object and the subject. This understanding of transitivity is considered to be exclusively a structural configuration (“syntactic transitivity”), thus distinguishing between two types of clauses: a transitive clause containing a direct object and a subject, and an intransitive clause containing only a subject (see, e.g., Dixon 1994).

However, recent approaches give more weight to semantic roles (“semantic transitivity”) that are typically found to correlate with the above-mentioned syntactic configuration. Following Hopper & Thompson (1980), this type of conceptualization treats transitivity as a type of “continuum”, comprising of different semantic and discourse features argued to be associated with the degree of transitivity. In this view, a given clause should not be characterized as transitive vs. intransitive, but rather as a more or less transitive (see, e.g., Næss 2007). Nevertheless, Haspelmath (2015: 136) states that this scalar view of transitivity is not best suitable for measuring transitivity cross-linguistically and argues that a more rigorous way of defining transitivity is needed so that each coding frame in a given language can be classified unambiguously as transitive or not.

The ‘Comrian’ approach (the label was coined by Haspelmath 2011, following Comrie 1989: 111), therefore, renders Hopper & Thompson’s continuum of semantic transitivity binary by defining transitivity on the basis of a prototypical transitive event in a specific language, such as ‘break’ or ‘kill’ (i.e., this event is identified semantically). In other words, a verb is considered transitive if it shows the same morphosyntactic properties (e.g., flagging, person indexing, or linear order) as the verb encoding the prototypical transitive event. This verb contains both an A and a P (or O) argument: A stands for an agent-like argument (micro-role ‘breaker’) and P for a patient-like argument (micro-role ‘broken thing’). These core arguments usually correspond to traditional notions of subject and direct object respectively.

The ‘Comrian’ approach, however, takes into account only bivalent verbs that are “canonically” marked as prototypical transitive verbs and does not consider other two-argument predicates in contrast to other approaches. For example, Dixon & Aikhenvald (2000: 3) considers bivalent verbs with oblique argument as “extended intransitives”, whose arguments are S (single/sole argument) and E (extension to core), and not A and P (or O).

Another approach to argument roles is offered by Witzlack-Makarevich (2011) and

Bickel (2011), which considers all bivalent verbs, but in contrast to Dixon & Aikhenvald (2000), regards A and P as generalized semantic argument roles that are not explicitly limited to a particular valency pattern. Therefore, any bivalent verb is considered to have an A and a P argument role, regardless of how it is marked or what its syntactic properties are. Accordingly, the “major” or “default” two-argument verb class is defined in terms of frequency, not prototypicality (see Haspelmath 2011 for an overview and comparison of the different approaches).

This thesis follows the ‘Comrian’ approach and hence the definition given by Haspelmath (2011) to transitivity, since this approach was also the one adopted for the accounts of different languages in the *Leipzig Valency Classes Project*. Although this exemplar-based approach may be regarded as arbitrary or intuition-based, in practice, all languages in the *ValPaL* database have the transitive class as their major verb class (Haspelmath 2015: 139).

3 The Persian language

The following section presents a brief overview of the Persian language with emphasis on specific features in its morphosyntax that are relevant for this thesis.

3.1 General remarks and state of study

Modern Persian (sometimes referred to as Farsi, Contemporary Persian, Standard Persian, New Persian, or simply Persian) is a South-Western Iranian language belonging to the Indo-Iranian branch of the Indo-European language family. It can be classified linguistically as a continuation of Middle Persian, the official language of the Sasanian Empire (3rd century BCE–7th century CE), and of Old Persian, the language of the Achaemenid Empire (6th–4th century BCE). Thus, it has been the prevalent language of Iranian lands and adjacent regions for over a millennium (Windfuhr & Jahani 2018: 455).

Figure 1: A geographic overview of the Iranian language family (Sedigheh 2020: 4)

Persian is one of the major languages in the Indo-Iranian branch, with more than 110 million speakers currently worldwide, mostly in Iran, Tajikistan, and Afghanistan where it serves as an official language (Figure 1). It is also called by its endonym *Farsi* in Iran, *Tajiki* in Tajikistan, and *Dari* in Afghanistan, all of which are mutually intelligible standard

varieties (Sedighi & Shabani-Jadidi 2018: 1). Since the Muslim conquest of Persia in the 7th century CE, Modern Persian has been written in a derived form of the Arabic script, which is used nowadays in Iran and Afghanistan (See Table 4 for the transliteration used in this thesis). In Tajikistan, on the other hand, Tajiki is written with a derivation of the Cyrillic script. The effects of the Muslim conquest of Persia and of the Arabic language are not limited to the Persian script, but are also heavily present in the lexicon (see, e.g., Perry 2002).

Research on the Persian language has previously focused on historical-diachronic linguistics, usually related to the ancient languages of Greater Iran, such as Old Persian, Avestan, and Middle Persian. However, in the past century Modern Persian has become an active topic of research, and many noteworthy volumes and papers on different linguistic subfields have been published across the world. The most widely studied is that of syntax, with an emphasis on topics such as scrambling (see e.g., Karimi 1999, 2003, 2008; Rasekh-Mahand 2003, and Adli 2010) and word order variation (Karimi 1989; Darzi 1996; Faghiri & Samvelian 2014, 2015, 2020, Faghiri et al. 2014, 2018; among others).

Other specific features of Persian syntax that have received a great deal of attention from different linguistic frameworks include the *ezāfe* construction (Samiian 1983, 1994; Ghomeshi 1997a; Samvelian 2007, 2008; Larson & Yamakido 2008; Haig 2011; Karimi & Brame 2012; Kahnemuyipour 2014; Larson & Samiian 2020; among others), the postposition =*rā* (Lazard 1982, 1994; Karimi 1989, 1990, 1996; Dabir-Moghaddam 1992; Ghomeshi 1997b; Ganjavi 2007; Jasbi 2020; Karimi & Smith 2020; among others), and complex predicates (Dabir-Moghaddam 1997; Karimi-Doostan 1997, 2005, 2011; Megerdooomian 2001, 2012; Folli et al. 2005; Samvelian 2012; Samvelian & Faghiri 2013b, 2014; Family 2014; among others).⁴ Most of the publications on these topics have been written from the perspective of the generative tradition. Nonetheless, Persian syntax and morphology has been studied in other linguistic fields.⁵

From a descriptive standpoint, the most comprehensive Persian grammar is that of Lazard (1992). The grammar is presented in the frame of descriptive-structuralist linguistics. It takes into account not only grammatical descriptions of Modern Persian, but also notes on different registers and periods (i.e., informal Persian and Classical Persian) and on variation of use. The examples in the grammar are given in the Persian orthography and are accompanied by English transliterations and translations. Drawing on Lazard

⁴See Samvelian (2018) for a more exhaustive overview of these specific features.

⁵See Ghomeshi (2018) and Karimi (2018) for a more comprehensive review of Persian Syntax.

(1992) are detailed linguistic descriptions by Mahootian (1997), Windfuhr (1979), Windfuhr & Perry (2009), Paul (2018), among others.

In the field of linguistic typology, research has focused on historical and areal comparisons of grammatical features across Iranian languages, such as word order (Dabir-Moghaddam 2001, 2006, 2013, 2018), alignment change (Haig 2008), and coordinating constructions (Stilo 2004).⁶ Apart from internal changes and genealogical affiliation, studies such as Stilo (2005, 2006, 2012, 2015), Haig & Khan (2018) and Haig & Rasekh-Mahand (2019) have also dealt with language contact and areal influence by other language families.

Research dealing exclusively with valency in Persian is relatively scarce. A notable exception is the *Syntactic Valency Lexicon for Persian Verbs* (Rasooli et al. 2011). Rasooli et al. (2011)'s notion of valency patterns in Persian is based on Tabibzadeh (2006), and the lexicon itself is a part of the *Persian Dependency Treebank Project* (Rasooli et al. 2013). Studies on Persian complex predicates have also take into consideration valency classes and alternations. Examples of such studies include publications by Family (2014), Samvelian & Faghiri (2013a), Samvelian et al. (2014), among others.

3.2 Basic morphosyntax

Prior to the discussion on valency classes and alternations, this section lays out the basics of Persian clause structure and case marking.

3.2.1 Clause structure

Persian is a nominative-accusative language with the basic word order of SOV.⁷ Arguments and adjuncts are almost exclusively coded by adpositions (see Section 3.2.4), which are used to express case relations. Persian also allows for Pro-drop, not only in the subject (S/A) position, but also, in appropriate contexts, in the direct object position (P/T). Example (5) illustrates both Pro-drops.

- (5) *vaqtike āmad-∅, be=h=eš mi-g-am.*
when come.PST-3SG to=3SG IPFV-say.PRS-1SG

‘As soon as (he) comes, (I) will tell (it) him.’ (Paul 2018: 590)

⁶Although these would not necessarily be considered strictly typological studies, as they focus on family-wide typological comparison, and do not disregard genealogy, they are still typological in nature and methodology, and some are even defined so by title.

⁷The formal register is quite conservative as to the canonical SOV order, whereas informal registers can show a considerable amount of variations. These variations are not all equally frequent and some suggest a special prosody (Paul 2018: 613-614).

3.2.2 Noun phrase and pronouns

Modern Persian has completely lost the Classical-Indo European nominal inflection of its ancestors, therefore, Persian nouns distinguish number and definiteness, but there is no morphological case system. All phrasal categories (other than the VP), namely, NP, PP, and CP are head-initial. The bare noun is generally ambiguous with respect to number and definiteness, i.e., *ketāb* can mean ‘book, a book, the book, books (as generic noun)’ (Paul 2018: 585). Number and definiteness of the bare noun are sometimes syntactically distinguishable.

Similar to nouns, Persian’s pronouns do not inflect for case. The full paradigm of pronouns is given in Table 1 (informal variants are given in round brackets). Like in some familiar European languages, among other languages, the 2PL *šomā*/*=etān* may be used to address the 2SG in polite discourse. A 3SG polite pronoun, originally plural, *išān* (lit. ‘they’), also exists, but is relatively rare and nowadays can no longer refer to the 3PL (Mahmoodi-Bakhtiari 2018: 281).

Table 1: Pronominal paradigm

	Independent	Enclitic		Independent	Enclitic	
1SG	<i>man</i>	<i>=am</i>	‘I’	1PL	<i>mā</i>	<i>=emān(=emun)</i> ‘we’
2SG	<i>to</i>	<i>=at(=et)</i>	‘you’	2PL	<i>šomā</i>	<i>=etān(=etun)</i> ‘you’
3SG	<i>u/vey(un)</i>	<i>=aš(=eš)</i>	‘he, she, it’	3PL	<i>ānhā(unhā)</i>	<i>=ešān(=ešun)</i> ‘they’

The pronominal enclitics may be bound to nouns (6a), as well as prepositions (5), and verbs, primarily in informal varieties. These denote the same grammatical functions as the independent pronouns, with the exception of the clause subject (Paul 2018: 591–592).⁸ In the case of a verb, the pronominal enclitics can be attached to simplex verbs, denoting direct object (6b) or indirect object (6c).

- (6) a. *barādar=am raft-Ø*.
brother=1SG go.PST-3SG
‘My brother left.’ [Elicited]
- b. *mi-bin-am=ešun*.
IPFV-see.PRS-1SG=3PL
‘I see them.’ [Elicited]
- c. *goft-am=et*.
say.PST-1SG=2SG
‘I told (it) to you.’ [Elicited]

⁸In informal registers, however, the third person singular pronominal enclitic may denote a clause subject, e.g., *āmad=eš come.PST=3SG* ‘he came’ (Paul 2018: 592).

The same is also true for *complex predicates*, whether the pronominal enclitic is attached to the *non-verbal element*, or the *light verb* (see Section 3.2.6 for definitions and further information). Examples (7a-7c) exhibit this type of alternation with the same complex predicate *bağal kardan* ‘to hug’ (lit. ‘bosom do’). Combinations of more than one pronominal enclitic are not possible.

- (7) a. *u=rā bağal kard-am.*
 3SG=DOM bosom do.PST-1SG
 ‘I hugged her.’ [Elicited]
- b. *bağal=eş kard-am.*
 bosom=3SG do.PST-1SG
 ‘I hugged her.’ [Elicited]
- c. *bağal kard-am=eş.*
 bosom do.PST-1SG=3SG
 ‘I hugged her.’ [Elicited]

3.2.3 *Ezāfe*

The *ezāfe*⁹ construction is a specific feature of many Western Iranian languages that has piqued the interest of different scholars for many years. One of the most debated topic in Persian linguistics is the status of the *ezāfe* itself and its functions (Samvelian 2018: 231). The Persian *ezāfe* is an enclitic, realized as =(y)e, which attaches to the head of the NP and links it to its modifiers (and modified modifiers, if present), nominal (including possessives) or adjectival, as illustrated in (8a) and (8b) respectively.

- (8) a. *xāne=ye pedar*
 house=EZ father
 ‘the father’s house.’ (Paul 2018: 611)
- b. *mard=e bozorg*
 man=EZ big
 ‘the big man.’ (Paul 2018: 611)

Samvelian (2018: 227–243) gives a comprehensive summary of the *ezāfe* phenomenon, focusing on its analyses as a case marker, a phonological linker, a head-marking affix, and a marker associated with a syntactic movement of the noun (roll-up movement). Nevertheless, almost all of the relevant literature focuses on *ezāfe* as a part of the nominal phrase system.

⁹The term itself, originating from Arabic *idāfa*, literally means ‘addition, adjunction’.

Windfuhr & Perry (2009: 476) argue that a few participles and adjectives, mainly original Arabic active and passive participles, when forming a complex predicate may take the *ezāfe*. In other words, for some complex predicates, the *ezāfe* flags an argument where the argument appears between the non-verbal element and the light verb.

For example, the complex predicate *‘āšeq budan* ‘to be in love’ is comprised of the Arabic active participle *‘āšeq* ‘lover’ as its non-verbal element, and of *budan* ‘to be’ as its light verb. In (9) the stimulus argument *doxtar* ‘the girl’ is linked via the *ezāfe* to the non-verbal element and appears before the light verb.

- (9) *u ‘āšeq=e doxtar ast.*
 3SG lover.PTCP=EZ girl be.PRS.3SG
 ‘He is in love with the girl.’ (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 476)

More on this valency frame is explained in Section 5.3.4.

3.2.4 Adpositions

Modern Persian adpositions can be classified into four categories (Paul 2018: 594-601): (simple) prepositions which are used without an *ezāfe*; (‘derived’) prepositions which are linked to their complement via an *ezāfe* (= [*y*]e); prepositional expressions, i.e., combinations of adverbs or adjectives with simple prepositions; and the enclitic postposition =*rā* (on which, see Section 3.2.4.2).

Persian principally uses its different adpositions to express case relations. The following seven prepositions are the most commonly used to flag arguments and adjuncts that are relevant for this thesis:

- *be*: ‘to, towards’. Dative, directional, goal, manner and means. According to Windfuhr & Perry (2009: 441), this is the most frequent preposition, and it is typically used to flag the indirect object of ditransitive verbs.
- *dar*: ‘in(side)’. Locative and directional. In informal registers, it is often replaced by the synonym *tu(=ye)* (lit. ‘the inside [of]’) (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 441).
- *az*: ‘from’. Ablative, source, partitive and passage.
- *bā*: ‘with’. Instrumental, comitative and concessive.

- *bar*: ‘on(to), upon, at’. Mostly locative. According to Windfuhr & Perry (2009: 442), this preposition occurs largely in literary Persian in fixed prepositional expressions and has been mostly replaced by the synonym *ru(=ye)* (lit. ‘(sur)face’).
- *barā=ye*: ‘for’. Benefactive, purposive, and causative. In informal registers, it is often replaced by its synonym *vāse(=ye)* (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 441).
- *sar=e*: ‘at’. Directional. The literal meaning of *sar=e* is ‘the head of’ and it is used primarily in informal registers (Lazard 1992: 196).

3.2.4.1 Omission of adpositions

Mostly in informal registers, the prepositions expressing location (10a), goal (10b) or indirect objects (10c), mainly *dar* ‘in’ or *be* ‘to’, may be dropped (Paul 2018: 596):

- (10) a. *man tehrān=am.*
 1SG Tehran=COP.PRS.1SG
 ‘I’m (in) Tehran.’ (Paul 2018: 596)
- b. *raft-am tehrān.*
 go.PST-1SG Tehran
 ‘I went (to) Tehran.’ (Paul 2018: 596)¹⁰
- c. *un=o be-deh-∅ ‘ali!*
 it=DOM IMP-give.PRS-2SG Ali!
 ‘Give it (to) Ali!’¹¹ [Elicited]

3.2.4.2 The postposition =*rā*

The enclitic postposition =*rā* (=ro/=o in informal registers) has been one of the most intensively discussed topics—if not the main topic—in numerous publications of the Persian language. It is the only postposition found in Modern Persian, whose major function is to flag certain direct object NPs. This type of phenomenon is often called *differential object marking* (glossed DOM),¹² i.e., flagging some but not all direct objects of verbs due to

¹⁰Although the predicate canonically appears after the indirect object/goal argument, it is probably less common in informal registers. The change in word order co-occurs with the omission of the preposition.

¹¹see Footnote 10, and see Faghiri & Samvelian (2014), Faghiri et al. (2014), Faghiri et al. (2018), and Faghiri & Samvelian (2020) for recent corpus and experimental based studies on the relative ordering of direct objects and indirect objects.

¹²The term itself was coined by Bossong (1985, 1991). DOM is a sub-type of *differential argument marking* (DAM), defined broadly by Seržant & Witzlack-Makarevich (2018: 3) as “Any kind of situation where an argument of a predicate bearing the same generalized semantic argument role may be coded in different ways, depending on factors other than the argument role itself, and which is not licensed by diathesis alternations.” In the case of Persian’s =*rā*, since its appearance is triggered by a cluster of features and therefore it marks said features, I chose to gloss it in this thesis as DOM.

various syntactic, semantic and discourse parameters. Analyzing the interaction between these parameters to account for the occurrence of =*rā* continues to be an intriguing challenge for different studies of the Persian language (Jasbi 2020: 119; Samvelian 2018: 226; Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 597; among others).

In Modern Persian, =*rā* is obligatory with all definite direct objects (Lazard 1992: 183; Mahootian 1997: 56; Windfuhr 1979: 442; among many others). This implies that pronouns, proper nouns, NPs introduced by a definite determiner (e.g., demonstrative, interrogative), anaphoric NPs, and NPs whose reference is one of a kind or given by the context, must be =*rā*-flagged in the direct object position, as exemplified in (11) (Samvelian 2018: 244).

- (11) *šoma=rā/ maryām=rā/ ān doxtar=rā/ noxost vazir=e farānse=rā*
 2PL=DOM/ Maryam=DOM/ DEM girl=DOM/ prime minster=EZ France=DOM
did-am.
 see.PST-1SG
 ‘I saw you/ Maryam/ that girl/ the French prime minster.’ (Samvelian 2018: 244)

However, definiteness cannot account for the whole range of =*rā* occurrences: while it constitutes a sufficient condition for =*rā*-flagging of direct objects, it is not a necessary condition, because indefinite objects may also be =*rā*-flagged, as shown in (12).

- (12) *maryām zan=i(=rā) dar kuče did-∅.*
 Maryam woman=INDF(=DOM) in street see.PST-3SG
 ‘Maryam saw a woman in the street.’ (Samvelian 2018: 244)

Some scholars have therefore suggested that *specificity*, rather than definiteness, is responsible for =*rā*-flagging (Browne 1970; Karimi 1990, 1996, 2003; among others). This viewpoint holds that all specific objects, whether definite or indefinite, must be =*rā*-flagged. Samvelian (2018: 245) points out that the concept of specificity lacks an agreed-upon definition, and explains that informally, a referent of a specific indefinite expression can be identifiable to the speaker, but not to the listener.

Contrary to this categorical viewpoint, some researchers maintain that the appearance of =*rā* is triggered not by a single binary feature (such as definiteness or specificity), but rather a cluster of features or properties, such as animacy, the semantic ‘distance’ between the verb and the object, the relative weight of the syntactic constituents, and information structure (Dabir-Moghaddam 1992; Faghiri & Samvelian 2014, 2015; Ghomeshi 1997b; Lazard 1982, 1994, 1992; among others). Example (13) shows the use of =*rā* with generic objects, proving thus that specificity is not a sufficient condition either.

- (13) *jāni=rā mojāzāt mi-kon-and.*
murderer=DOM punishment IPFV-do.PRS-3PL
‘Murderers are punished.’ (lit. ‘They punish murderers.’) (Lazard 1994: 170)

Another feature that may trigger the appearance of =*rā* is high transitivity. In this regard, =*rā* may flag oblique arguments, such as a semantic locative or dative, which would otherwise have a prepositional realization. Compare (14a) and (14b):

- (14) a. *zamine=e pošt=e bāġ=rā lubiyā kāšt-am.*
ground=EZ behind=EZ garden=DOM bean plant.PST-1SG
‘I have planted beans in the ground behind the garden.’ (Samvelian 2018: 245)
- b. *dar zamine=e pošt=e bāġ lubiyā kāšt-am.*
in ground=EZ behind=EZ garden bean plant.PST-1SG
‘I have planted beans in the ground behind the garden.’ (Samvelian 2018: 246)

Contrary to prepositional realization, =*rā*-flagged arguments receive a holistic reading, in the sense that they ‘measure out’ or delimit the event described by the verb (Lazard 1982; Ghomeshi 1997b). In other words, in (14a) beans were planted in the entire ground, whereas in (14b) the beans were planted in a section of the ground. Therefore, (14a) and (14b) do not display the same truth conditions (Samvelian 2018: 246).

Another alternation that may occur with =*rā* is the so-called *dative alternation* in English (*to give somebody something* vs. *to give something to somebody*). In example (15a), the goal or beneficiary argument *hezār nafar* ‘1,000 people’ is followed with =*rā*, whereas in (15b) it is introduced by the canonical preposition *be* ‘to’.

- (15) a. *mašalan bejā=ye pānšad nafar, emšab hezār nafar=rā dar*
for example instead=EZ five hundred person, tonight thousand person=DOM in
mašjed=e āzarbāijāni-hā šām be-dah-ad.
mosque=EZ Azerbaijani-PL dinner SBJV-give.PRS-3SG
‘For example, instead of 500 people, tonight, he’d better offer dinner to 1,000 people at the Azerbaijanis’ mosque.’ (Samvelian 2018: 245)
- b. *be hezār nafar šām mi-dah-ad.*
to thousand person dinner IPFV-give.PRS-3SG
‘He offers dinner to 1,000 people.’ (Samvelian 2018: 246)

It has been demonstrated that the interplay of numerous criteria, such as definiteness, animacy, and discourse accessibility (or givenness), favors the double object variant (Bresnan et al. 2007). Samvelian (2018: 246) argues that at first glance, these criteria have a role in the preference for the double object construction in Persian as well, but this phenomenon requires further investigation.

It should be noted that the use of the =*rā* is not limited to flagging objects, and it is also used as a topicalizer for other non-subject constituents, as illustrated in (16). Meanwhile, a more detailed discussion is beyond the scope of this thesis (for further discussions see Lazard 1982, Dabir-Moghaddam 1992, Samvelian 2018, Jasbi 2020, among others).

- (16) *emeruz=rā dars mi-x^w ān-am.*
 today=TOP lesson IPFV-read.PRS-1SG
 ‘As for today, I (will) study.’ (Faghiri & Samvelian 2014: 219)

3.2.5 Persian verbal system

Every Persian verbal form is based on two stems: stem 1, traditionally called *present stem* (PRS), and stem 2, traditionally referred to as *past stem* (PST). The past stem itself can be derived directly from the infinitive (by removing the suffix *-an*), while the relationship between the present stem and the infinitive is not always transparent. Compare the examples in Table 2.

Table 2: Persian infinitives and stems

	Infinitive	Past stem	Present stem
‘to do’	<i>kardan</i>	<i>kard</i>	<i>kon</i>
‘to hit’	<i>zadan</i>	<i>zad</i>	<i>zan</i>
‘to have’	<i>dāštan</i>	<i>dāšt</i>	<i>dār</i>
‘to give’	<i>dādan</i>	<i>dād</i>	<i>deh</i>

Finite verbs are based on the two stems, and with different affixations, verbal particles, and auxiliaries, the entire verbal system is formed. Each finite form is inflected for person, number¹³, voice, negation, tense, aspect and mood (TAM). However, TAM are not always clearly distinguished from each other, thus it is easier for one to describe nine basic finite forms of the verb based on each stem: the past stem is used to form the simple past (preterit), past progressive (imperfect) and past perfect (pluperfect). The present stem is used to form the present (indicative),¹⁴ present perfect, imperative, (simple) subjunctive and perfect subjunctive.

Persian has a split verbal lexicon with two major types of verbs: simplex verbs (i.e., monolexic) and compound verbs, referred to here as complex predicates. Simplex verbs

¹³It is worth noting: “Number indexation of the subject of all verbs is sensitive to animacy, though this sensitivity has weakened through [the] history [of Modern Persian]” (Dabir-Moghaddam 2018: 78). See also Lazard 1992: 179; Paul 2018: 587; among others.

¹⁴The present may also express the future, especially in informal registers (Paul 2018: 606). A periphrastic form with the present stem of the verb *x^w āstan* ‘to want’ as an auxiliary verb can also express the future, but it is used primarily in formal registers or for emphatic purposes (Mahmoodi-Bakhtiari 2018: 291).

take affixes directly whereas for complex predicates, the light verb takes all the inflectional and derivational affixes, while the nominal element takes none.

3.2.6 Complex predicates

Persian has around 250 simplex verbs, only half of which are currently used in everyday speech. Although verbification from nouns is possible (e.g., *raqs* ‘dance’ > *raqs-idan* ‘to dance’), such examples are rare, and *complex predicates* (CPrs)¹⁵ are the main device used in forming and enriching the verbal lexicon of Persian (Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a: 11).

In layman’s terms, a Persian complex predicate is a multiword expression that consists of at least two parts: a verbal element, known as the *light verb* (LV), and a *non-verbal element* (NVE) that usually precedes it. The non-verbal element can be a noun, e.g., *ħarf zadan* ‘to talk’ (lit. ‘talk hit’), an adjective, e.g., *penhān kardan* ‘to hide’ (lit. ‘concealed do’), a preverb,¹⁶ e.g., *bar dāstan* ‘to take’ (lit. ‘PREV have’), or a prepositional phrase, e.g., *be kār bordan* ‘to use’ (lit. ‘to work carry’). There are no phonological or morphological constraints on the non-verbal element, and in the case of a noun, many times it can be modified, i.e., pluralized, take DOM, adjectives, enclitic pronouns, and indefinite markers.

Identifying the type of constructions that can be considered complex predicates has been a focus of many linguistic studies on Persian (Dabir-Moghaddam 1997; Sedighi 2009; Samvelian 2012; among others). Samvelian (2018: 256–257) points out that the boundary line between complex predicates and ordinary object-verb combinations is drastically blurred from semantic and syntactic points of view. Semantically, due to the limited number of simplex verbs in Persian, most of them have a vague semantic meaning which becomes specific only in the context of their combination with their arguments. In other words, there is some degree of arbitrariness in deciding whether an object-verb combination qualifies as a complex predicate. Syntactically, criteria that are used to identify complex predicates, such as single-word stress and limited syntactic autonomy of the non-verbal element, also apply to object-verb combinations.

The most striking piece of evidence illustrating both semantic and syntactic points of view is the variability of complex predicates listed in Persian dictionaries, which changes

¹⁵This type of verbs are also referred to as *Compound Verbs*, *Light Verb Constructions*, or *Phrasal Verbs*.

¹⁶This type of non-verbal element is also referred to as *particle* or *prefixal*. A preverb is a morpheme that appears in front of a verb and form a close semantic unit with it (Booij & Van Kemenade 2003: 1). In Modern Persian, preverbs are a closed category of former adverbs, nouns or prepositions that no longer function independently and are more or less opaque (Perry 2007: 1016). If a complex predicate is composed of non-verbal element(s) and a preverb, the preverb is the last constituent before the light verb, e.g., *qadam bar dāstan* ‘to pace’ (lit. ‘step(s) PREV have’).

significantly from one dictionary to another. Therefore, Samvelian (2018: 257) argues that the issue of identifying the type of constructions that can be considered as complex predicates is still up to debate, presumably because whether a combination is a complex predicate or not is usually a matter of usage and lexicalization rather than the combination's self inherent properties.

Other issues regarding Persian complex predicates, such as understanding their formation processes, syntactic properties, separability, productivity, and semantic characteristics, have also been popular research topics in Persian linguistics for many years (Dabir-Moghaddam 1997; Karimi-Doostan 1997, 2011; Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a, 2014; Family 2014; among others). The majority of studies have focused on the dual nature of complex predicates, which exhibit both lexical and phrasal properties. On the one hand, Persian complex predicates display all the properties of syntactic combinations, including some degree of semantic compositionality, while, on the other hand, they also have word-like properties, such as lexicalization, idiomaticity, and the fact that the sequence can undergo morphological operations (Samvelian 2018: 257).

Although Persian complex predicates formation exhibits all the hallmarks of a lexeme formation process, Samvelian (2018: 260–261) concludes that none of the arguments supporting the “wordhood” of Persian complex predicates are conclusive, and that Persian complex predicates exhibit all typical properties of syntactic combinations and parallel object-verb combinations in Persian.

Another issue that has received a great deal of attention is that of compositionality (Megerdooian 2001, 2012; Folli et al. 2005; Samvelian 2012; Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a,b, 2014; among others). The prevailing approach has been in favor of a “fully” compositional view of Persian complex predicates, according to which the respective contributions of the non-verbal element and the light verb of a complex predicate are consistent through all their combinations and can be defined *a priori* (Megerdooian 2001, 2012; Folli et al. 2005; among others). For instance, Folli et al. (2005: 1378–1379) claim that the verb *dāštan* ‘to have’ is only used to form stative complex predicates, giving *dust dāštan* ‘to love’ (lit. ‘friend have’) as an example. However, as it has been shown in recent studies (Samvelian 2012: 114–130, Samvelian 2018: 267, Samvelian & Faghiri 2013b: 216, Samvelian & Faghiri 2014: 57), the verb *dāštan* is not invariably stative and can give rise to eventive (dynamic) complex predicates such as *ersāl dāštan* ‘to send’ (lit. ‘sending have’), *taqdim dāštan* ‘to offer’ (lit. ‘offering have’), *e’elām dāštan* ‘to announce’ (lit. ‘announcing have’), etc.

Furthermore, since numerous complex predicates are semantically opaque (Goldberg 1996; Karimi-Doostan 1997, 2005; Family 2008, 2014; Samvelian 2012; Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a; among others), the meaning of a Persian complex predicate cannot be predictable, consequently rendering a fully compositional approach impractical. This means that one is not able to derive the meaning of a complex predicate based on the meaning of its components, and even in the case of transparent complex predicates, the meaning is usually conventional and has to be learned (Samvelian 2018: 267–268).

Based on such observations, Samvelian (2012) and Samvelian & Faghiri (2013a,b, 2014) developed a construction-based approach of compositionality, which they qualify as *a posteriori*, in the sense that Persian complex predicates are comparable to *Idiomatically Combining Expressions*, that is “idioms whose parts carry identifiable parts of their idiomatic meanings” (Nunberg et al. 1994: 496). In other words, the light verb and the non-verbal element of a complex predicate can be assigned a meaning in the context of their combination. Therefore, a complex predicate is compositional, in the way that its meaning can be distributed to its components, and yet it is idiomatic, in the way that the contribution of each component cannot be determined out of the context of its combination with the other one (Samvelian 2018: 269). For instance, the expression *spill the beans* is conventional or idiomatic, in that it must be learned and cannot be driven from its component parts, and yet it is still compositional, in that its meaning can be distributed among its components. In the context of its association with *beans*, *spill* means ‘to divulge’, and in the context of its association with *spill, beans* mean ‘secrets’ (Samvelian & Faghiri 2014: 65).

Nevertheless, it is hard to determine to what extent the verbal lexicon is comprised of complex predicates that are compositionally non-transparent (idiomatic) as opposed to transparent complex predicates (non-idiomatic), such as *dard kardan* ‘to feel pain, to ache’ (lit. ‘pain do’) vs. *kār kardan* ‘to work’ (lit. ‘work do’), respectively. The more idiomatic a complex predicate is, the easier it is to define it as a unified lexical item and not a verb and a complement.

The construction-based approach offered by Samvelian (2012) and Samvelian & Faghiri (2013a,b, 2014) is based on the assumption that despite their idiomaticity, each Persian complex predicate corresponds to a construction that can be grouped into classes based on their syntactic and semantic similarities. These classes can be represented by a partially fixed number of constructions (i.e., valency frames), that can later be structured in networks such as valency alternations (Samvelian & Faghiri 2014: 72; Samvelian 2018: 268).

4 Date and methods

The following section covers the corpora used in this thesis and the methodological steps taken to analyze the retrieved data from said corpora.

4.1 Corpora

The data used in this thesis were gathered from four sources: the *TalkBank* Persian corpus provided via Sketch Engine;¹⁷ the *PersPred* database provided by the research unit Mondes iranien et indien;¹⁸ *Sulayman Hayyim's New Persian-English dictionary* available via the Digital Dictionaries of South Asia (DDSA) program of the University of Chicago and the Center for Research Libraries;¹⁹ and three native language consultants. Examples taken from each source are referenced as 'TalkBank', 'PersPred', 'Hayyim', or 'Elicited' respectively in square brackets.

The *TalkBank* Persian corpus is a written Persian corpus made out of blog posts from various Persian blog sites collected by Shlomo Argamon's research group at Illinois Institute of Technology (IIT). It contains about 305 million tokens,²⁰ which correspond to around 270 million words or 14.5 million sentences. Each token is lemmatized and tagged for part-of-speech using the *Persian Syntactic Dependency Treebank* (Rasooli et al. 2013).

The corpus can be accessed using the Sketch Engine website, which provides an online platform with different tools to retrieve and analyze the data in this corpus. These include word sketch (Persian collocations categorized by grammatical relations), a thesaurus (synonyms and similar words for every word), keywords (terminology extraction of one-word and multi-word units), word lists (lists of Persian nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc. organized by frequency), n-grams (frequency list of multi-word units), text type analysis (statistics of metadata in the corpus), and a concordance (examples in context).

For the purpose of this thesis, I used the concordance feature to search for the relevant verbs and predicates. Using the CQL²¹ search function, relevant verbs were searched in a specific context that can yield the desired valency frame or alternation. For example, the complex predicate *ħarf zadan* 'to talk (to X) (about Y)' (lit. 'speech hit') allows for

¹⁷<https://www.sketchengine.eu/talkbank-persian-corpus/>

¹⁸<https://www.perspred.cnrs.fr/>

¹⁹<https://dsal.uchicago.edu/dictionaries/hayyim>

²⁰A token is the smallest unit that a corpus consists of. A token normally refers to words, digits, punctuation marks, etc.

²¹The *Corpus Query Language* (CQL) is a special code or query language used in Sketch Engine to search for complex grammatical or lexical patterns or to use search criteria that cannot be set using the standard user interface. It is used to set criteria for positions or tokens, i.e., words, lemmas, tags, etc.

an uncoded alternation with regards to the Y argument: it can be flagged either by the preposition *az* (lit. ‘from’) or by an *ezāfe* on the non-verbal element (which must also be flagged by *=rā* in the case of a pronominal argument, see Section 3.2.4.2).

Figure 2 shows the first CQL used to search for the complex predicates *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk (to X) (about Y)’ (lit. ‘speech hit’) with the prepositional valency frame: the first bracketed sequence is the preposition *az* (lit. ‘from’), the second one is an independent pronoun (tagged as ‘SEPER’), and the last two bracketed sequences indicate the non-verbal element and the light verb of the complex predicate *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk’. This search yielded a total of 65 results, some are given in Figure 3.

Figure 2: CQL search for *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk’ with the preposition *az* ‘about’ (lit. ‘from’)

Figure 3: Examples of *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk’ with the preposition *az* ‘about’ (lit. ‘from’)

Along the same lines, Figure 4 shows the CQL used to search for the same verb, but with the *ezāfe* argument alternation: the first bracketed sequence is the non-verbal element of the complex predicate (*ḥarf*), the second one is an independent pronoun, the third is the postposition *=rā*, and the last is the light verb of the complex predicate (*zadan*). This search yielded a total of 27 results, some are given in Figure 5.

The second corpus, *PersPred*, is a multilingual syntactic and semantic database for Persian complex predicates (Samvelian & Faghiri 2013a). It is an ongoing project that provides not only an inventory of Persian complex predicates, but also a rich syntactic and semantic annotation for each of them, along with translations to English and French. Each complex predicate is illustrated by one or more attested examples from various sources. Building

Figure 4: CQL search for *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk’ with the *ezāfe* argument (+ =*rā*)

	Details	sentence
1	<input type="checkbox"/> blogfa.com	<S/> شما حرف ما را زدید اما بعد در سایتها می بینم همه من و سریالم را تخطیه می کنند.
2	<input type="checkbox"/> blogfa.com	<S/> من همیشه نمی توانم حرف تو را بزدم ارش.
3	<input type="checkbox"/> jahannnews.com	<S/> از او پرسیدیم مردم ما چه کتابهایی را می خردند و پاسخ شنیدیم مردم شعرهایی را می خردند که حرف آنها را بزند.
4	<input type="checkbox"/> khaandaniha.com	<S/> اصولگرایان حرف شما را نمی زنند.

Figure 5: Examples of *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk’ with the *ezāfe* argument (+ =*rā*)

on Samvelian (2012), the first release of the database (*PersPred 1*) included around 700 complex predicates with *zadan* ‘to hit’ as their light verb, whereas the present version includes more than 1,500 complex predicates with various light verbs, e.g., *dādan* ‘to give’, *gereftan* ‘to take’, *āvardan* ‘to bring’, etc.

The third resource, used for the contextual examples which it provides, is *The New Persian-English dictionary: Complete and Modern* by Sulayman Hayyim (1962). This dictionary is considered one of the most dependable and widely used bilingual dictionaries of Persian (Assi 2018: 310). It consists of two volumes, containing the English meanings of over 50,000 words, terms, idioms, and proverbs in the Persian language, as well as the transliteration of the words in English characters.

For the purpose of this thesis, the dictionary provided information regarding transitivity and certain examples of specific predicates were taken. Every example taken from any of the aforementioned corpora was checked by three native language consultants, two living in Israel and one living in the Netherlands. Some examples were also elicited when the corpora were lacking sufficient examples.

4.2 The Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes

Similar to the descriptions of different languages in the two volumes of *Valency Classes in the World's Languages* (Malchukov & Comrie 2015a,b) and the *ValPaL* online database, this

thesis follows the methodological steps developed by the *Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes* (Malchulov et al. (2015)).²²

The purpose of the questionnaire is to gather comparable valency data on a wide variety of languages. Hence, it includes a selected set of 70 core verb meanings in English, alongside a typical context,²³ that are perceived as representative of the verbal lexicon. These verbs have been attested in the literature to exhibit distinctive syntactic tendencies both within and across languages. Contributors of the *Leipzig Valency Classes Project* were required to provide counterpart verbs in their respective languages for each of the pre-defined verb meanings. The number of verb meanings may vary depending on further verb meanings selected as interesting by individual contributors of the project. As for this thesis, 87 core verb meanings were selected (See Table 5 in the Appendix).

Apart from counterpart verbs, contributors were also asked to provide coding frames (as manifested by flagging, indexing and/or word order), valency alternations (both coded and uncoded), and glossed examples showcasing said coding frames and alternations for each verb. The availability of alternation types and their distribution across different verbs differ from one language to another. Hence, the project members were especially interested in alternations that are relevant to verb classification in the sense that they are neither restricted to few verbs, nor apply to the entire verbal lexicon (Hartmann et al. 2013).

This thesis follows the conventions used in the questionnaire to represent coding frames and their coding elements (flags and indexes) with some modifications. The major conventions are listed in (17).

- (17) 1. Adpositions are represented by their form, linked to the argument by a plus (+) sign, preceding it for prepositions, e.g., *be+2*, *az+3*, etc., or following it for postpositions, e.g., *2+rā* (see Section 3.2.4 about adpositions). The *ezāfe* argument marking that occurs on the non-verbal element has been treated the same for the sake of representation, e.g., *NVE=EZ+2* (see Section 3.2.3 about the *ezāfe*).
2. Index sets are represented by their category labels, linked to the verb by a period, e.g., *V.SUBJ* for Persian subject agreement. The index label is im-

²²An online extended version of the questionnaire, referred to as the *Database Questionnaire Manual*, is also available at <https://ValPaL.info/database>.

²³It should be noted that clausal arguments, i.e., complement-clause arguments such as *that*-clauses and infinitival clauses in English, are not considered a typical context and were excluded from *ValPaL*, and hence in this thesis as well. The reason being that the typology of complement clauses is treated as separate domain of study (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 56).

mediately followed by square brackets which contain the argument number, so V.SUBJ[1] means that the agreement index-set corresponds to argument 1 (usually corresponds to S or A semantic roles).

3. Locational arguments are notated with LOC, followed by the argument number. Thus, the coding frame of verbs such as *nešastan* ‘to sit down’ is <1 (LOC2) V.SUBJ[1]>.
4. Optional arguments are enclosed in round brackets.²⁴

²⁴The question of optionality is a difficult concept that relates, among other things, to the distinction between arguments and adjuncts. Hence, this convention was not strictly enforced in *ValPaL* (Haspelmath & Hartmann 2015: 55).

5 Valency classes in Persian

This section introduces Persian's valency classes with their typical coding frames. For most valency patterns, the subject is not flagged and is indexed on the verb (exceptions are patterns in Sections 5.2.2 and 5.3.3). As mentioned previously, the object argument may be flagged by =*rā*, and indirect arguments are flagged using prepositions or *ezāfe* (see Sections 3.2.4 and 3.2.3). There are ten major valency classes, one avalent, two monovalent, four bivalent, and three trivalent.

5.1 Avalent predicates: coding frame <(NVE) V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>

Avalent verbs are rare. Plausible examples are meteorological complex predicates, such as *bārān āmadan* (lit. 'rain come') and *barf āmadan* (lit. 'snow come'). These verbs tend to appear with a temporal or locative adjunct (18a). The verb *bāridan* (lit. 'to rain') can take something that falls from the sky as its non-verbal element, e.g., 'rain', 'hail', 'snow' (18b), etc.

- (18) a. *diruz bārān āmad-∅.*
yesterday rain come.PST-3SG
'It rained yesterday.' (lit. 'rain came yesterday.') [TalkBank]
- b. *diruz barf barid-∅.*
yesterday snow rain.PST-3SG
'It snowed yesterday.' (lit. 'snow rained yesterday.') [Elicited]

It is worth noting that the non-verbal element in cases such as (18a) and (18b) may also be analyzed as a subject argument, thus the predicate will be regarded as a monovalent-intransitive simplex verb (see Section 5.2.1). However, this analysis depends on one's definition of complex predicates and therefore goes beyond the scope of this thesis.

5.2 Monovalent predicates

Monovalent predicates include only intransitive predicates. Two monovalent valency classes are found in Persian.

5.2.1 Intransitive: coding frame <1 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

Intransitive predicates regularly agree with their sole argument (i.e., the subject), regardless of the meaning of the verb. This class of predicates includes not only verbs, whether

simplex, such as *xandidan* ‘laugh’ (19a), or complex predicates, such as *ġalt zadan* ‘to roll’ (lit. ‘roll hit’) (19b), but also nominal predicates, such as *šekārči* ‘hunter’ (19c), or adjectival predicates, such as *xošk* ‘dry’ (19d).

- (19) a. *in doxtar ziyād mi-xand-ad.*
 DEM girl many IPFV-laugh.PRS-3SG
 ‘This girl laughs a lot.’ [Hayyim]
- b. *piyāz-hā ġalt zad-and ru=ye zamin.*
 onion-PL roll hit.PST-3PL on=EZ ground
 ‘The onions rolled on the ground.’ [TalkBank]
- c. *pedar va ‘amu-hā=yam šekārči bud-and.*
 father and uncle-PL=1SG hunter COP.PST-3PL
 ‘My father and uncles were hunters.’ [TalkBank]
- d. *10 šobḥ zamin xošk bud-Ø.*
 10 morning ground dry COP.PST-3PL
 ‘At 10 o’clock in the morning the ground was dry.’ [TalkBank]

5.2.2 Intransitive: coding frame <(1) NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>

The only type of predicates that do not show agreement on the verb is the so-called *experiencer subject construction*,²⁵ in which the experiencer argument is flagged by the pronominal enclitic (Table 1) on the non-verbal element, and the light verb itself takes the default third-person singular index (20). Therefore, this valency frame is only available for complex predicates, which tend to express physical or psychological processes/states and are a growing class in informal registers (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 487). The optional experiencer in the clause-initial position, e.g., *man* ‘I’ in (20), acts as a topicalized subject (Sedighi 2009: 69).

- (20) (*man*) *sard=am=e.*
 (TOP.1SG) cold=1SG=be.PRS.3SG
 ‘I’m cold.’ [Elicited]

A similar type of construction is also attested with bivalent predicates (see Section 5.3.3).

²⁵This construction is also referred to as *Psychological Predicate Construction*, *Impersonal Construction*, *Inalienable possessor construction*, *Impersonal Complex Predicates*, and *Pronominal Complex Predicates*. See Ghomeshi (2018: 216-217) and Karimi (2018: 172-174) for more information.

5.3 Bivalent predicates

Bivalent predicates include both intransitive and transitive predicates. Four bivalent valency classes are found in Persian, one transitive and three intransitive:

5.3.1 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+RĀ (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

This valency frame is typically associated with dynamic (non-stative) transitive verbs, whether they are simplex verbs, such as *koštan* ‘kill’ (21a), or complex predicates, such as *kotak zadan* ‘to beat’ (lit. ‘beating hit’) (21b).

- (21) a. *magas=ro košt-am (bā magas koš=i qermez).*
fly=DOM kill.PST-1SG (with fly swatter=INDF red).
‘I killed the fly (with a red fly swatter).’ [TalkBank]
- b. *čerā pedar=aš=rā kotak zad-and?*
why father=3SG=DOM beating hit.PST-3PL
‘Why did they beat her father?’ [TalkBank]

The majority of these verbs seem to govern patient-like object arguments, but not exclusively, e.g., verbs of possession (e.g., *dāštan* ‘to have’), perception (e.g., *didan* ‘to see’), or even psychological state (e.g., *dust dāštan* ‘to love’ [lit. ‘friend have’]) also appear in this valency frame, as shown in (22).

- (22) a. *nāme=ye šoma=rā dār-am.*
letter=EZ 2PL=DOM have.PRS-1SG
‘I have your letter.’ [Elicited]
- b. *mard xers=rā did-Ø.*
man bear=DOM see.PST-3SG
‘The man saw the bear.’ [Elicited]
- c. *man in bāzi=ra dust dār-am.*
1SG DEM game=DOM friend have.PRS-1SG
‘I love this game.’ [TalkBank]

5.3.2 Intransitive: coding frame <1 PP+2 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

This valency class includes different types of verbs. For instance, verbs that require an agent argument and its location or goal, whether simplex, such as *nešastan* ‘to sit’ (23a) or *raftan* ‘to go’ (23b), or complex predicates, such as *bāla raftan* ‘to climb’ (lit. ‘upwards go’) (23c) or *zendgi kardan* ‘to live’ (lit. ‘life do’) (23d).

Other verbs in this valency class include *fekr kardan* ‘to think (about)’ (lit. ‘thought do’), *tarsidan* ‘to fear, to be afraid (of)’, *negāh kardan* ‘to look (at)’ (lit. ‘look do’), *dād/gīg zadan* ‘to shout/scream (at)’ (lit. ‘shout/scream hit’) and *dast zadan* ‘to touch’ (lit. ‘hand hit’). In the case of complex predicates, the non-verbal element can also appear before the prepositional argument. For example, in (23e) the non-verbal element *negāh* ‘look’ appears before the preposition *be* ‘at’ (lit. ‘to’).

- (23) a. *pesar ru=ye zamin nešast-∅.*
 boy on=ez floor sit.PST-3SG
 ‘The boy sat (down) on the floor.’ [TalkBank]
- b. *zan be bāzār raft-∅.*
 woman to market go.PST-3SG
 ‘The woman went to the market.’ [Elicited]
- c. *az deraxt bālā raft-∅.*
 from tree upwards go.PST-3SG
 ‘He climbed the tree.’ (lit. ‘from the tree’) [Hayyim]
- d. *man dar āmrikā zendgi mi-kon-am.*
 1SG in US life IPFV-PRS.do-1SG
 ‘I live in the US.’ [TalkBank]
- e. *negāh be čehre=āš kard-am.*
 look to face=3SG do.PST-1SG
 ‘I looked at her face.’ [TalkBank]

As mentioned in Section 3.2.4.1, the preposition marking the second argument may be dropped in informal registers. Furthermore, the entire prepositional argument may be omitted when it is known or generic.

5.3.3 Intransitive: coding frame <(1) PP+2 NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]>

Similar to the valency class shown in Section 5.2.2, the experiencer argument for this type of predicates is flagged by the pronominal enclitic (Table 1) on the non-verbal element, whereas the light verb takes the default third-person singular index. This valency class includes complex predicates, such as *xoš āmādan* ‘to like’ (lit. ‘pleasure come’), *yād raftan* ‘to forget’ (lit. ‘memory left’), and *herš gerftan* ‘to get pissed off/to get furious’ (lit. ‘rage take’), which take a prepositional phrase as an argument, usually the preposition *az* ‘from’, which express stimulus. This argument may appear before (24a) or after (24b) the non-verbal element.

- (24) a. *(man) az in rang xoš=am mi-yā-d.*
 (TOP.1SG) from DEM color pleasure=1SG IPFV-come.PRS-3SG
 ‘I like this color.’ / ‘This color pleases me.’ [Elicited]
- b. *herš=am az=at gereft-Ø.*
 rage=1SG from=2SG take.PST-3SG
 ‘I’m pissed off by you.’ [Elicited]

5.3.4 Intransitive: coding frame <1 NVE=EZ+2 V.SUBJ[1]>

This valency frame is only available for complex predicates. It entails two arguments, the first one is the unflagged subject (or the agent), and the second one is referred to in the literature as the *ezāfe complement* (Rasooli et al. 2011: 228), and in this thesis called the *ezāfe argument*.²⁶ The *ezāfe* argument appears between the non-verbal element and the light verb of a complex predicate, linked to first by the *ezāfe*. For example, in (25) the goal argument *doktor* ‘doctor’ is flagged by the *ezāfe* thus appearing between the non-verbal element and the light verb of the complex predicate *donbāl raftan* ‘to follow’ (lit. ‘behind go’).

- (25) *pesar-ak dar=e dokkān=rā bast-Ø va donbāl=e doktor raft-Ø.*
 boy-DIM door=EZ shop=DOM close.PST-3SG and behind=EZ doctor go.PST-3SG
 ‘The little boy closed the shop’s door and followed the doctor.’ [TalkBank]

It is worth noting that only two complex predicates, viz. *donbāl raftan* ‘to follow’ (lit. ‘behind go’) and *donbāl gaštan* ‘to search (for)’ (lit. ‘behind turn’), exhibit this valency frame exclusively, and all other predicates that can take the *ezāfe* argument can also alternate with another prepositional argument (see Section 6.2.2).

5.4 Trivalent predicates

Trivalent predicates include both intransitive and transitive predicates. Three trivalent valency classes are found in Persian, two transitive and one intransitive.

5.4.1 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+RĀ PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

This coding frame is commonly used with verbs denoting some sort of transfer, such as transfer of possession, e.g., *dādan* ‘to give’, *gereftan* ‘to take/get’, *ersāl kardan* ‘to send’ (lit. ‘sending do’), etc., or transfer of information or knowledge, e.g., *goftan* ‘to say’, *nemudan* ‘to show’, *yād dādan* ‘to teach’ (lit. ‘memory give’), etc. These types of verbs can be simplex

²⁶This argument is called *mafūl-e nešāne-ye ezāfe-i* in Persian (Tabibzadeh 2006).

or complex predicates, as exemplified in (26). The order of the direct object (argument 2) and the indirect object (argument 3) may change due to different criteria and constraints such as length and salience (see e.g., Faghiri et al. 2014, 2018).

- (26) a. *pul=rā az u gereft-am.*
 money=DOM from 3SG take.PST-1SG
 ‘I took/got the money from him.’ [Hayyim]
- b. *in maṭlab=rā barāy=e mā ersāl kard-and.*
 DEM article=DOM for=EZ 1PL sending do.PST-3PL
 ‘They sent us this article.’ (lit. ‘They sent this article for us.’) [TalkBank]
- c. *rāh=e ḥal=e mas’ale=rā be u yād dād-am.*
 way=EZ solution=EZ problem=DOM to 3SG memory give.PST-1SG
 ‘I taught him the solution for the problem.’ (lit. ‘I taught the solution of the problem to him.’) [Hayyim]

Other verb classes included in this valency class are verbs of putting, e.g., *gozāštan* ‘to put’ (27a), verbs of throwing, e.g., *andāxtan* ‘to throw’ (27b), verbs of combining and attaching, e.g., *bastan* ‘to tie’ (27c), and verbs of separating and disassembling, e.g., *kandan* ‘to tear’ (27d).

- (27) a. *ketāb=rā ru=ye miz be-gozār-Ø.*
 book=DOM on=EZ table IMP-put.PRS-2SG
 ‘Put the book on the table.’ [Hayyim]
- b. *tup=rā be-andāz-Ø dar havā.*
 ball=DOM IMP-throw.PRS-2SG in air
 ‘Throw the ball into the air.’ [Hayyim]
- c. *qaṣṣāb gāv=rā bā ṭanab be deraxt bast-Ø.*
 butcher cow=DOM with rope to tree tie.PST-3SG
 ‘The butcher tied the cow to the tree with a rope.’ [TalkBank]
- d. *barge=rā az daftar kand-Ø.*
 sheet=DOM from notebook tear.PST-3SG
 ‘She tore the sheet of paper from the notebook.’ [TalkBank]

5.4.2 Transitive: coding frame <1 2+RĀ 3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

This coding frame is associated with verbs that are referred to in the literature as taking *predicative complements* (Levin 1993: 180-185; among others), and in this thesis as *predictive arguments*.²⁷ The predicative argument can be a noun or an adjective, ascribing a property to the direct object (argument 2) of the verb.

²⁷This argument is called *tamiz* in Persian (Tabibzadeh 2006).

The predicative argument is not flagged and appears after the direct object and before the verb, whether the verb is a simplex verb, such as *nāmidan* ‘to name’, *dānstan* ‘to consider’, etc., or a complex predicate, such as *e‘elām kardan* ‘to declare, to announce (X as Y)’ (lit. ‘announcement do’), *maḥsub kardan* ‘to consider, to count (X as Y)’ (lit. ‘calculated do’), etc.

Notice that unlike prepositional arguments that allow some degree of word order variation, due to the lack of flagging on the predicative argument, its position in the clause is strict. In other words, constituent order plays a role in defining predicative arguments. Consider the examples in (28).

- (28) a. *man u=rā dust mi-dān-am.*
 1SG 3SG=DOM friend IPFV-consider.PRS-1SG
 ‘I consider him a friend.’ (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 488)
- b. *u=rā ebrāhim namid-and.*
 3SG Ebrahim name.PST-3SG
 ‘They named him Ebrahim.’ [Hayyim]
- c. *ānhā u=rā barande e‘elām kard-and.*
 3PL 3SG=DOM winner declaration do.PST-3PL
 ‘They declared her the winner.’ / ‘They announced her as the winner.’ [Elicited]

5.4.3 Intransitive: coding frame <1 PP+2 PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]>

The only verb in the sample displaying this coding frame is the complex predicate *ḥarf zadan* ‘to talk (to X about Y)’ (lit. ‘speech hit’), as shown in (29):

- (29) a. *bā dust-ān=e mān mi-tavān-im az hame čiz ḥarf be-zan-im.*
 with friend-PL=1PL IPFV-can.PRS-1PL from all thing speech SBJV-hit.PRS-1PL
 ‘We can talk to our friends about anything.’ [TalkBank]
- b. *bā in hame nafar čerā ḥarf az kambud-hā mi-zan-id?*
 with DEM all person why speech from deficiency-PL IPFV-hit.PRS-2PL
 ‘Why are you talking about the deficiencies with all these people?’ [TalkBank]
- c. *dar mored=e in ketāb bā ham(digar) ḥarf zad-im.*
 in subject=EZ DEM book with each(other) speech hit.PST-1PL
 ‘We talked to each other about this book.’ (lit. ‘we talked about this book with each other.’) [TalkBank]

The ‘about’ argument can appear before (29a) or after (29b) the non-verbal element *ḥarf* ‘speech’. In examples (29a) and (29b) it is expressed using the preposition *az* ‘from’,

but it can be expressed with any prepositional expression denoting the same meaning, as exemplified in (29c).

6 Valency alternations in Persian

The following section describes the different valency alternations found in Persian, i.e., patterns where predicates with one and the same core lexical meaning are compatible with two or more coding frames. These alternations can be divided into two types: The first type is coded alternations, i.e., valency alternations in which the predicate is involved, usually by morphological/syntactical marking. The second type is uncoded alternations, i.e., valency alternations which are realized only by the choice of argument flagging.

6.1 Coded alternations

Persian has two coded alternations in which the predicate undergoes a change, namely the passive and the causative.

6.1.1 Passive

In this thesis I follow Zúñiga & Kittilä's (2019: 83) definition: passive is a coded syntactic valency-reducing operation, which is characterized by the reduction of the syntactic valency by one, compared to the active counterpart. Furthermore, the passive subject corresponds to the non-subject P of the active counterpart, whereas the subject A of the active counterpart is peripheral, and optional.

The Persian passive is used when the agent is unknown or irrelevant (Mahootian 1997: 143; Paul 2018: 609; among others).²⁸ It is formed with the past participle form of the lexical verb followed by the conjugated auxiliary verb *šodan* 'to become' (Lazard 1992: 162; Paul 2018: 609; among others). Compare the active example in (30a) with the passive example in (30b).

- (30) a. *ketāb=rā xarid-am.*
book=DOM buy.PST-1SG
'I bought the book.' [Elicited]
- b. *ketāb xarid-e šod-Ø.*
book buy.PST-PTCP become.PST-3SG
'The book was bought.' [Elicited]

In formal registers, an agent may be added with the preposition *az* 'from, by' or with prepositional expressions, such as *be vasile=ye* 'by means of', *az taraf=e* 'on behalf of' (lit.

²⁸Another common way of indicating an unspecified agent is the use of the third person plural indexing without an overt subject (e.g., 13) (Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 499).

‘from the side of’), *be dast=e* ‘by the hand of’, etc. (Lazard 1992: 162). Another auxiliary verb, viz. *gaštan/gardidan* ‘to turn, to become’, can also be used in formal registers (Lazard 1992: 162; Paul 2018: 609).

The passive of complex predicates may be formed in the same way as outlined above or by replacing the light verb with a different light verb that will provide a passive reading. For instance, the complex predicate *pāsox dādan* ‘to answer’ (lit. ‘answer give’) forms a regular periphrastic passive in (31). Example (32) shows the light verb *xordan* ‘to collide’ replacing the light verb *dādan* ‘to give’ to provide a passive reading for the CPrs *šekast dādan* ‘to defeat’ (lit. ‘defeat give’).

- (31) a. *ostād be so’ālāt=emān pāsox dād-∅.*
 teacher to questions=1PL answer give.PST-PST-3SG
 ‘The teacher answered our questions.’ [Elicited]
- b. *so’ālāt=emān pāsox dād-e šod-∅.*
 questions=1PL answer give.PST-PTCP become.PST-3SG
 ‘Our questions were answered.’ [Elicited]
- (32) a. *tim=e šomā tim=e mā=rā šekast dād-∅.*
 team=EZ 2PL team=EZ 1PL=DOM defeat give.PST-3SG
 ‘Your team defeated our team.’ (Karimi 2018: 189)
- b. *tim=e mā (az tim=e šomā) šekast xord-∅.*
 team=EZ 1PL (from team=EZ 2PL) defeat collide.PST-3SG
 ‘Our team was defeated (by your team).’ (Karimi 2018: 189)

6.1.2 Causative

A valency increasing operation, the causative is formed by adding the suffix *-ān* to the present stem of certain simplex verbs. The derived causative verbs are always transitive, whether the corresponding simplex verb is intransitive (33a) or transitive (34a) (Lazard 1992: 290; Windfuhr & Perry 2009: 488).

- (33) a. *kimeā xandid-∅.*
 Kimea laugh.PST-3SG
 ‘Kimea laughed.’ (Karimi 2018: 192-193)
- b. *parivz kimeā=rā xand-ān-d-∅.*
 Parivz Kimea=DOM laugh.PRS-CAUS-PST-3SG
 ‘Parviz made Kimea laugh.’ (Karimi 2018: 192-193)

- (34) a. *bačče keyk=rā xord-∅.*
 child cake=DOM eat.PST-3SG
 ‘The child ate the cake.’ [Elicited]
- b. *mādar keyk=rā be bačče xor-ān-d-∅.*
 Mother cake=DOM to child eat.PRS-CAUS-PST-3SG
 ‘The mother fed the cake to the child.’ / ‘The mother made the child eat the cake.’ [Elicited]

With regards to complex predicates, replacing the light verb with a different light verb, usually *kardan* ‘to do, to make’, may many times provide a causative reading. Consider the examples in (35) and (36).

- (35) a. *barf āb šod-∅.*
 snow water become.PST-3PL
 ‘The snow melted.’ (Karimi 2018: 191)
- b. *xoršid barf=rā āb kard-∅.*
 sun snow=DOM water do.PST-3SG
 ‘The sun melted the snow.’ (Karimi 2018: 192)
- (36) a. *vāred=e kelās šod-im*
 arrive.PTCP=EZ class become.PST-1PL
 ‘We entered the class.’ [Elicited]
- b. *ostād mā=rā vāred=e kelās kard-∅*
 teacher 1PL=DOM arrive.PTCP=EZ class do.PST-3SG
 ‘The teacher brought us into the class.’ / ‘The teacher made us enter the class.’
 [Elicited]

In (36b), the light verb *kard* (lit. ‘did’) replaces the light verb *šod* (lit. ‘became’) in (36a), providing a causative reading. Do note that the complex predicate *vāred šodan* ‘to enter’ (lit. ‘arrive.PTCP become’) is active although containing the light verb *šodan*, used also for the regular passive.

6.2 Uncoded alternations

Persian has a number of uncoded alternations, i.e., valency alternations that are not marked on the predicate, but are attained through changing the flagging of arguments. Although Persian exhibits some subject-demoting alternations (e.g., the verbs *šekāstan* ‘to break’ and *boridan* ‘to cut’ allow for Levin’s (1993) *inchoative causative alternation*) and some object-demoting alternations (e.g., the verbs *xordan* ‘to eat’ and *bāzi kardan* ‘to play’ (lit. ‘game

do') allow Levin's (1993) *unspecified object-alternation*), most of the uncoded alternations found in this thesis are *object rearranging alternations*. These types of alternations can be indicated by different adpositions or by the *ezāfe*. The different uncoded alternations can be divided into three groups: =*rā* alternations, *ezāfe* alternations, and other prepositional alternations.

6.2.1 =*rā* alternations

As mentioned in Section 3.2.4.2, =*rā* can act as a transitivizer for arguments that would usually be flagged by a preposition.

6.2.1.1 =*rā* and *be* 'to' alternation: Dative alternation

Apart from the verb *dādan* 'to give' shown in (15), seven verbs were found that allowed this type of alternation (37). One simplex verb, viz. *zadan* 'to hit', and six complex predicates, viz. *lebās pušāndan* 'to dress' (lit. 'clothing cover'), *komak kardan* 'to help' (lit. 'help do'), *negāh kardan* 'to look (at)' (lit. 'look do'), *kotak zadan* 'to beat' (lit. 'beating hit') and *dast zadan* 'to touch' (lit. 'hand hit'). These verbs do not seem to belong to one common lexical class. Some examples are shown in (37).

- (37) a. *mādar doxtar=aš=rā lebās pušānd-Ø.*
 mother daughter=3SG=DOM clothing cover.PST-3SG
 'The mother dressed her daughter.' [Elicited]
- b. *ziyād be kudak lebās na-pušān-id.*
 much to baby clothing NEG.IMP-cover.PRS-2PL
 'Do not dress the baby too much.'²⁹ [TalkBank]
- c. *ān pir mard=rā komak kard-and.*
 DEM old man=DOM help do.PST-3PL
 'They helped that old man.' [Hayyim]
- d. *be ān pir mard komak kard-and.*
 to DEM old man help do.PST-3PL
 'They helped that old man.' [Hayyim]
- e. *omid be čāne=aš dast zad-Ø.*
 Omid to chin=3SG hand hit.PRS-3SG
 'Omid touched his chin.' [TalkBank]
- f. *movāzeb bāš-Ø ān=rā dast na-zan-i!*
 careful be.IMP.PRS-2sg DEM=DOM hand NEG.SBJV-hit.PRS-2PL
 'Be careful not to touch that!' [TalkBank]

²⁹In this instance, the preposition *be* 'to' can also alternate with the preposition *bar* 'on'.

6.2.1.2 =*rā* and *bā* ‘with’ alternation: Reciprocal alternation

One verb was found demonstrating this alternation, which is the complex predicate *molāqāt kardan* ‘to meet (formally)’ (lit. ‘meeting do’), as shown in (38).

- (38) a. *mān bā u dar xāne=aš molāqāt kard-am.*
1SG with 3SG in house=3SG meeting do.PST-1SG
‘I met him in his house.’ (lit. ‘I met with him at his house.’) [TalkBank]
- b. *u=rā dar xiyāban molāqāt kard-am.*
3SG=DOM in street meeting do.PST-1SG
‘I met him in the street.’ [Hayyim]
- c. *u va man (hamdigar=rā) dar xiyāban molāqāt kard-im.*
3SG and 1SG (each other=DOM) in street meeting do.PST-1PL
‘She and I met (each other) in the street.’ [Elicited]

6.2.1.3 =*rā* and LOC alternation: Locative alternation

Apart from the verb *kāštan* ‘to plant’ shown in (14), the only verb that was found demonstrating this alternation is the CPrs *bār kardan* ‘to load’ (lit. ‘load do’), as shown in (39).

- (39) a. *tamām=e asbāb-a=ru tu vānet bār kard-∅.*
all=EZ furniture-PL=DOM in pick-up truck load do.PST-3SG
‘He loaded all the furniture onto the pick-up truck.’ [PersPred]
- b. *vānet=rā mive bār kard-∅.*
pick-up truck=DOM fruit load do.PST-3SG
‘He loaded the pick-up truck with fruit.’ [Elicited]

Notice that unlike English, the second argument in (39b) is not flagged at all, similar to the predicative argument (see Section 5.4.2).

6.2.2 *Ezāfe* alternations

These alternations are only available for complex predicates. The *ezāfe* argument was found to alternate with both a direct object (= *rā*-flagged argument) or an indirect object (prepositional argument). For example, the complex predicate *pust kandan* ‘to peel’ (lit. ‘skin tear’) is a bivalent complex predicate that allows the direct object to alternate with the *ezāfe* argument, as shown in (40).

- (40) a. *sib=rā pust be-kan-Ø!*
 apple=DOM skin IMP-tear.PRS-2SG
 ‘Peel the apple!’ [Hayyim]
- b. *pust=e xiyār-hā=rā koloft mi-kand-Ø.*
 skin=EZ cucumber-PL=DOM thickly IPFV-tear.PST-3SG
 ‘He peeled the cucumbers thickly.’ [PersPred]

In (41), the same alternation occurs but with an indirect object: the bivalent complex predicate *fekr kardan* ‘to think (about X)’ (lit. ‘thought do’) can occur either with a prepositional argument meaning ‘about’, in this instance the preposition *be* (lit. ‘to’),³⁰ or with the *ezāfe* argument.

- (41) a. *in ruz-hā modām be to fekr mi-kon-am.*
 DEM day-PL continually to 2SG thought IPFV-do.PRS-1SG.
 ‘I keep thinking about you these days.’ [TalkBank]
- b. *man hālā dige ašlān fekr=e to=ro ne-mi-kon-am.*
 1SG now further ever thought=EZ 2SG=DOM NEG-IPFV-do.PRS-1SG
 ‘Now I don’t ever think about you anymore.’ [TalkBank]

It is worth noting that the *ezāfe* argument can additionally be flagged with =*rā*, whether the complex predicate is transitive (40) or intransitive (41).

The *ezāfe* alternation can also occur with trivalent complex predicates. For example, the intransitive complex predicate *ħarf zadan* ‘to talk (to X) about (Y)’ (lit. ‘speech hit’) allows for the alternation with regards to the ‘about’ argument, in this instance the preposition *az* (lit. ‘from’),³¹ as shown in (42).

- (42) a. *bā dust-ān=emān mi-tavān-im az hamē ċiz ħarf be-zan-im.*
 with friend-PL=1PL IPFV-can.PRS-1PL from all thing talk SBJV-hit.PRS-1PL
 ‘We can talk to our friends about anything.’ (lit. ‘We can talk with our friends from anything.’) [TalkBank]
- b. *vaqti mādar=aš ħarf=e ān boqče=rā mi-zad-Ø...*
 when mother=3SG talk=EZ DEM BUNDLE=DOM IMPV-hit.PST-3SG
 ‘When his mother was talking about that bundle...’ [PersPred]

In the case of transitive trivalent complex predicates, containing both direct object and an indirect object, the alternation seems to be possible only with regards to the indirect object. For example, the complex predicate *yād dādan* ‘to teach (X) to (Y)’ (lit. ‘memory

³⁰The ‘about’ argument can be flagged by other prepositional expressions denoting the same concept, e.g., *dar mored=e* lit. ‘in subject of’, *dar bāre=ye* lit. ‘in regard of’, etc.

³¹see Footnote 30.

give’) is a transitive complex predicate that takes a theme as a direct object and a recipient as an indirect object. In (43), the recipient argument can be realized either as a prepositional argument (43a), or as an *ezāfe* argument (43b).

- (43) a. *rāh=e ḥal=e mas’ale=rā be u yād dād-am.*
 way=EZ solution=EZ problem=DOM to 3SG memory give.PST-1SG
 ‘I taught him the solution to the problem.’ (lit. ‘I taught the solution to the problem to him.’) [Hayyim]
- b. *rāh=e ḥal=e mas’ale=rā yād=e u dād-am.*
 way=EZ solution=EZ problem=DOM memory=EZ 3SG give.PST-1SG
 ‘I taught him the solution to the problem.’ [Elicited]

The *ezāfe* argument can alternate with other prepositional arguments. Beside the adpositions =*rā* (DOM), *be* (lit. ‘to’), and *az* (lit. ‘from’) shown in the above-mentioned examples, it can also alternate with a LOC denoting preposition. For example, in (44) the complex predicate *bār kardan* ‘to load’ (lit. ‘load do’) exhibit the *ezāfe* alternation with regards to the LOC argument, marked with *tu* ‘in’ (44a).

- (44) a. *tamām=e asbāb-a=ru tu vānet bār kard-∅.*
 all=EZ furniture-PL=DOM in pick-up truck load do.PST-3SG
 ‘He loaded all the furniture onto the pick-up truck.’ [PersPred]
- b. *se ruz ba’ad vasā’el=ro bār=e kāmyun kard-im.*
 three day later items=DOM load=EZ truck do.PST-1PL
 ‘Three days later we loaded the items onto the truck.’ [TalkBank]

According to Windfuhr & Perry (2009: 476), the *ezāfe* argument can also alternate with a prepositional argument flagged with *bā* ‘with’. They give the example of the Arabic active participle ‘*āšeq* ‘lover’ as shown in (9). However, at least for this predicate, no instance of such alternation was found in the corpora and the *bā* ‘with’ flagged option was not deemed grammatical by the language consultants.

6.2.3 Other prepositional alternations

A few other alternations between some prepositions or prepositional expressions were found in regard to some predicates. For example, a few transfer verbs allow an alternation with regards to the recipient argument, viz. the simplex verb *ferstādan* ‘to send (X) to (Y)’, its complex predicate synonym *ersāl kardan* (lit. ‘sending do’), and the complex predicate *ta’arif kardan* ‘to tell’ (lit. ‘narrative do’). Example (45) shows the recipient argument of

the complex predicate *ta'arif kardan* 'to tell' (lit. 'narrative do') flagged by the preposition *barā=ye* 'for' and by the preposition *be* 'to'.

- (45) a. *dāstān=rā barā=ye mādar ta'arif mi-kon-ad.*
story=DOM for=EZ= mother narrative IPFV-do.PRS-3SG
'She tells the story to (her) mother.' [TalkBank]
- b. *dar ḥal=i ke mi-xandid-am jaryān=o be=h=eš ta'arif kard-am.*
in state=RSTR COMP IPFV-laugh.PST-1SG current=DOM to=3SG narrative do.PST-1SG
'I told him the current events while I was laughing.' [TalkBank]

Another alternation includes *be* 'to' and *bar* 'on' for the recipient argument in the verbs *xandidan* 'laugh at' and *lebās pušāndan* 'to dress' (lit. 'clothing cover'), or the location argument for the verb *bastan* 'to tie'.

7 Discussion

Based on 87 different core verb meanings in Modern Persian, 94 predicates were analyzed and described for their valency coding frames and alternations (see Table 5). There are a couple of reasons for this discrepancy: first, some core verb meanings have more than one verb realization (or verb lemma), e.g., the core verb meaning of ‘SEND’ can be realized either by the simplex verb *ferstādan* or the complex predicate *ersāl kardan* (lit. ‘sending do’), both meaning ‘to send’.³²

Second, some verb lemmas have more than one verb core meaning, e.g., the verb *xan-didan* ‘to laugh’ can act as a monovalent verb taking only a subject argument, i.e., the core verb meaning is ‘S LAUGH’, or it can act as a bivalent verb taking a subject and a ‘goal/receptient’ argument, i.e., the core verb meaning is ‘A LAUGH at X’.

Out of 94 predicates, 42 are simplex verbs and 52 are complex predicates, displaying a total of 31 different coding frames that can be grouped into ten valency classes: one aivalent, two monovalent, four bivalent, and three trivalent. These ten valency classes can be divided based on their transitivity, as shown in (3).

Table 3: Valency classes divided by transitivity

Transitivity	Valency class	Number of predicates
TR	1 2+ $\bar{r}\bar{a}$ (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	24
TR	1 2+ $\bar{r}\bar{a}$ PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	21
TR	1 2+ $\bar{r}\bar{a}$ 3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	6
INTR	1 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	20
INTR	1 PP+2 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	13
INTR	1 PP+2 PP+3 (NVE) V.SUBJ[1]	1
INTR	(1) NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]	1
INTR	(1) PP+2 NVE=[1] V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]	3
INTR	1 NVE=EZ+2 V.SUBJ[1]	3
Avaelnt	(NVE) V.SUBJ[DFLT.3SG]	2
Total:		94

Beside the aivalent class, three valency classes are transitive (i.e., regularly takes = $\bar{r}\bar{a}$), and six are intransitive.³³ Although there are more intransitive valency classes, out of 94

³²According to the *ValPaL* guidelines (Hartmann et al. 2013), authors were asked to choose the verb lemmas which are considered as having “basic” flavor, i.e., morphologically less complex and/or more frequent. In the case of several basic items, authors were asked to include all verb lemmas. With regard to Persian, morphologically less complex verbs, or in other words, simplex verbs, are many times less common than their complex predicate counterparts. Furthermore, frequency information could not be attained due to the syntactic behavior (e.g., separability) of the complex predicate. Therefore, I relied on the language consultant’s intuition and if there were any doubts, I gave more than one option.

³³Notice that some uncoded alternations may change the transitivity of the predicate, this will be explained later.

different predicates, more than 50% are transitive in nature. This finding corresponds to other languages documented in *ValPaL*, i.e., the transitive class is the major verb class in the Persian language (Haspelmath 2015: 139).

With respect to valency alternations, there are two coded alterations, namely the passive and the causative forms. The Persian passive is relatively regular, and almost all the transitive predicates allow it. There are few exceptions of predicates that display a transitive valency pattern, but do not allow for the passive alternation, e.g., *molāqat kardan* ‘to meet’ (lit. ‘meeting do’), *dust dāštan* ‘to love’ (lit. ‘friend have’), and *bağal kardan* ‘to hug’ (‘bosom do’). The reason for the lack of alternation is probably due to the semantic nature of these verbs, but this requires further investigation.

Interestingly, there are three intransitive verbs that allow for the passive alternation, viz. *āvāz x^w āndan* ‘to sing’ (lit. ‘song read’), *dast zadan* ‘to touch’ (lit. ‘hand hit’), and *negāh kardan* ‘to look at’ (lit. ‘look do’). When the complex predicate *āvāz x^w āndan* ‘to sing’ (lit. ‘song read’) appears in the passive, i.e., *āvāz x^w ānd-e šod-∅* (lit. ‘the song was read’), one can argue that it is no longer a complex predicate, and that in the new construction the non-verbal element, *āvāz* ‘song’, is now the subject, hence these are two different constructions. The same can also be said for *dast zadan* ‘to touch’ (lit. ‘hand hit’) and *negāh kardan* ‘to look’ (lit. ‘look do’) that change to *dast xordan* ‘to be touched’ (lit. ‘hand collide’) and *negāh oftādan* ‘to be looked’ (lit. ‘look fall’) respectively, but these require further investigation.

The causative alternation seems to be much less productive in Persian: only 17 predicates were found to allow the causative, most of them are simplex verbs, such as *tarsidan* ‘to fear’ > *tarsāndan* ‘to frighten’, *suxtan* ‘X burns’ > *suzāndan* ‘to cause X to burn’, and *xandidan* ‘to laugh’ > *xandāndan* ‘to cause X to laugh’. It should be noted that a few causative alternations, namely of the simplex verbs *rixtan* ‘to pour’, *šekastan* ‘to break’, and *bāridan* ‘to rain’, are attested in *Sulayman Hayyim’s New Persian-English dictionary*, but are considered rather rare by the language consultant and also do not seem to appear as much in the corpora.

With respect to uncoded alternations, three groups of object rearranging alternations were attested: =*rā* alternations, *ezāfe* alternations, and other prepositional alternations. A total of 23 different predicates exhibit one of these alternations, and 5 predicates exhibit more than one alternation. The first group is the =*rā* alternations, in which an argument that is usually flagged by a preposition is flagged with the postposition =*rā*. This group includes the dative-alternation (e.g., *I gave him the book* vs. *I gave the book to him*), the

reciprocal alternation (e.g., *David met Anna* vs. *David and Anna met*), and the locative alternation (e.g., *I loaded the truck with hay* vs. *I loaded hay onto the truck*). A total of 9 predicates were found to exhibit one of these alternations.

The second group is the *ezāfe* alternations, in which an argument can be linked to the non-verbal element of a complex predicate via *ezāfe* flagging. The *ezāfe* argument can alternate with a direct object, or an indirect object, depending on the transitivity of the complex predicate. A total of 10 predicates were found to exhibit an *ezāfe* alternation, 3 for the direct object and 7 for the indirect object. As noted in Section 6.2.2, the *ezāfe* argument can sometimes be additionally flagged with *=rā*. In the case of verbs whose basic valency patterns already take *=rā*, in other words are already transitive verbs, this behavior is not so interesting. On the other hand, this is an interesting behavior for verbs that are intransitive in nature, e.g., the complex predicate *ḥarf zadan* 'to talk about' (lit. 'speech hit'). Although this alternation does not change the basic verb meaning, it does change the semantic transitivity of the verb. I postulate that this is most likely due to the nature of the light verb, i.e., the simplex verb *zadan* 'to hit', can normally take *=rā*, whereas, e.g., *šodan* in *vāred šodan* 'to enter' (lit. 'arrive.PTCP become'), cannot. This question is heavily intertwined with the notions of compositionality and separability of the complex predicate and requires further research.

The third group of object rearranging alternations includes other prepositional alternations which appear to be less frequent, e.g., the preposition *be* 'to' can alternate with the preposition *barā=ye* 'for' with regards to the recipient argument for some predicates. A total of 9 predicates were found to exhibit a prepositional alternation, 7 of which involves *be* lit. 'to' as one of the prepositions. Other types of alternations that can be found in Persian are subject-demoting alternations, e.g., Levin's (1993) inchoative causative alternation (e.g., *I broke the window* vs *the window broke*) and object-demoting alternations, e.g., Levin's (1993) unspecified object-alternation (e.g., *I ate the cake* vs *I ate*). However, These types of alternations was not the focus of this thesis and requires further investigation.³⁴

One issue worth noting is that of the lack of statistics. The fact that the non-verbal element of a complex predicate can be modified and/or separated from its light verb poses a major issue when one wants to retrieve all the occurrences of said complex predicate from the corpora. On top of that, since prepositional arguments and *ezāfe* arguments can appear between the non-verbal element and the light verb, many times deciding which

³⁴In cases where such alternations were encountered, it was mentioned in a comment about the verb.

coding frame is the more “basic” one is rather hard, as accurate frequency data of each alternation are unavailable. For example, the complex predicate *komak kardan* ‘to help’ (lit. ‘help do’) can exhibit a =*rā* argument (dative alternation) or an alternate *ezāfe* argument, as shown in (46).

- (46) a. *be ān pir mard komak kard-and.*
to DEM old man help do.PST-3PL
‘They helped that old man.’(lit. ‘they helped to that old man’) [Hayyim]
- b. *ān pir mard=rā komak kard-and.*
DEM old man=DOM help do.PST-3PL
‘They helped that old man.’ [Hayyim]
- c. ... *hamun jā komak=e bačč-ha mi-kard-∅.*
... same place help=EZ child-PL IPFV-do.PST-3SG
‘... he used to help children there.’ [TalkBank]

In accordance with the guidelines offered by the *ValPaL* database (Hartmann et al. 2013), when a principled decision regarding which coding frame is the more “basic” and which is an alternation is difficult or impossible to make, an arbitrary decision can be taken. In such instances, I turned to the valency lexicon of Rasooli et al. (2011), which offers percentage of occurrences. However, many of the predicates investigated in this thesis do not appear in Rasooli et al. (2011), so I turned to the language consultant’s intuitions and to a bird eyes view of the results from the corpora used.

8 Conclusion

This thesis set out to describe the major valency frames and alternations in the Modern Persian. Following the methodological steps developed by the *Leipzig Questionnaire on valency classes (ValPaL)*, 87 different core verb meanings were chosen, which yielded 94 predicates that were gathered and analyzed for their valency data. A summary of the data can be seen in Table 5.

First, each predicate was annotated for its basic coding frame. In turn, 31 different coding frames were found, which were grouped into ten different valency classes: one aivalent, two monovalent, four bivalent, and three trivalent. Even though only three out of ten valency class are transitive in nature, as shown in Table 3, more than 50% of all predicates fall into one of these valency classes. In other words, the transitivity class is the major verb class in Modern Persian, similar to the other languages documented in *ValPaL* (Haspelmath 2015: 139).

Second, each predicate was also investigated and annotated for the availability of valency alternations. These alternations were then divided into two major groups: coded alternation and uncoded alternations. Persian exhibits two types of coded alternations, the passive and the causative. Passivization of transitive predicates is rather productive, whereas the causative form, whether of transitive or intransitive predicates, is far less productive. The different strategies for signaling the passive or the causative depends on whether the predicate is a simplex verb or a complex predicate, as explained in Section 6.1.

In regard to uncoded alternations, this thesis focused on a specific type of uncoded alternations, viz. object rearranging alternations. The different object rearranging alternations that were found were divided into three groups: *=rā* alternations, *ezāfe* alternations, and other prepositional alternations. The most unique group among the three is that of *ezāfe* alternations, which is only relevant for complex predicates and probably only found in Iranian languages, perhaps even only in Persian, as the *ezāfe* is a grammatical feature unique to Iranian languages and some unrelated neighboring languages. Nevertheless, out of the 52 complex predicates investigated in this thesis, only 10 were found to allow an *ezāfe* alternation. This poses the following question: what makes a complex predicate allow for the *ezāfe* alternation? Does it depend on the ‘original’ preposition which was altered? Or perhaps it depends on the semantic class of the complex predicate itself? Unfortunately, due to the low number of complex predicates exhibiting an *ezāfe*

alternation, a conclusion could not be attained. One hypothesis that come to mind is that this alternation depends on the nature of the relation between the non-verbal element and the light verb. For example, one can argue that *ħarf* ‘speech’ in *ħarf zadan* ‘to talk’ (lit. ‘speech hit’) is more ‘object like’, hence prone to modification such as taking an *ezāfe*, than, for example, *dast* ‘hand’ in *dast zadan* ‘to touch’ (lit. ‘hand hit’). This type of question is related to the compositionality and separability of the complex predicate and requires further investigation.

During the course of this thesis, a number of questions occurred to me that require future research. Suggested below are some of the topics worthy of further examination.

- Language acquisition and teaching: a study on how the different valency classes and alternations are learned by or taught to second language learners of the Persian language, especially idiosyncratic valency classes, such as the so called *experiencer subject construction* (Sections 5.2.2 and 5.3.3).
- Corpus linguistics: a statistical corpus-based research on the different alternations found in this thesis, especially alternations relevant only for complex predicates, such as the *ezāfe* alternations.
- Computational linguistics and natural language processing: a study on how the different valency classes and alternations can be implemented in a computer program such that it can predict other predicates that follow the same patterns.

To conclude, this thesis contributes to the growing number of studies in the field of typology and valency, since research dedicated specifically to valency patterns and alternations in Persian is quite scarce. Furthermore, Persian is a widely spoken language with great regional influence and its structurally interesting verbal features are worthy of typological attention. I hope this thesis has shed some light on the matter and will inspire others to further research Persian’s valency patterns and alternations and to conduct valency-related research in general.

Appendix

Table 4: Transliteration

Consonants															
<i>b</i>	ب	<i>p</i>	پ	<i>t</i>	ت	<i>s</i>	ث	<i>j</i>	ج	<i>č</i>	چ	<i>h</i>	ح	<i>x</i>	خ
<i>d</i>	د	<i>z</i>	ذ	<i>r</i>	ر	<i>z</i>	ز	<i>ž</i>	ژ	<i>s</i>	س	<i>š</i>	ش	<i>ṣ</i>	ص
<i>z</i>	ض	<i>t</i>	ط	<i>z</i>	ظ	‘	ع	<i>g</i>	غ	<i>f</i>	ف	<i>q</i>	ق	<i>k</i>	ک
<i>g</i>	گ	<i>l</i>	ل	<i>m</i>	م	<i>n</i>	ن	<i>v</i>	و	<i>h</i>	ه	<i>y</i>	ی	’	ء
Vowels and Diphthongs															
<i>ā</i>	آ/ا	<i>i</i>	ی	<i>u</i>	و	<i>a</i>	اَ	<i>e</i>	اِ	<i>o</i>	اُ	<i>ei</i>	عی	<i>ou</i>	ؤ

Table 5: Valency classes and alternations summary

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations			Uncoded Alternations		
					Causative	Passive	-rā and be (Dative alternation)	-rā alternations		
								-rā and ba (Incohesive alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	ezdfe alternations
1	RAIN	<i>barān āmadan¹</i>	NVE V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	RAIN	<i>barīdan²</i>	V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	+	-	-	-	-	-
2	BE DRY	<i>xoš budan³</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	BURN	<i>suxtān</i>	1 V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	+	-	-	-	-	-
4	SINK	<i>gerāz šodan⁴</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	+	-	-	-	-	-
5	ROLL	<i>galtīdan⁵</i>	1 V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	+	-	-	-	-	-
5	ROLL	<i>galt zadān⁶</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	+	-	-	-	-	-
5	ROLL	<i>galt xordān⁷</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	+	-	-	-	-	-
6	BE A HUNTER	<i>šakāre budan⁸</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	BE HUNGRY	<i>gorosne budan⁹</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	BE SAD	<i>narāpāt budan¹⁰</i>	1 NVE V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	DIE	<i>mordan</i>	1 V.subj[I]	1 V.subj[I]	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	FEEL COLD	<i>sard budan¹¹</i>	(0) NVE=CLT[I] V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	(0) NVE=I] V.subj[DFLT.3SG]	-	-	-	-	-	-

- Lit. 'rain come', a lexically fixed expression (expressions for 'snow', 'hail', etc. are formed in the same way). The NVE can be analyzed as the subject argument.
- An avalent verb, but can also be regarded as a monovalent verb taking sth. that falls from the sky, e.g. 'rain', 'snow', 'hail', etc. as its subject.
- Comprised of the adjective 'dry' + the copula 'to be'.
- Comprised of the adjective 'sunk' + the copula 'to become'.
- Can also be written *galtīdan*. Can have other meanings such as 'to roll over/toss in bed', 'to wallow/welter in the mud/in blood', '[tears] rolling/falling down', and 'to trundle'.
- NVE is derived from the LV *galtīdan* 'to roll' (#5). Can have other meanings such as 'to roll over/toss in bed', 'to wallow/welter in the mud/in blood', '[tears] rolling/falling down', and 'to trundle'. The difference between this verb and *galt zadān* (#5) (if any) requires further research.
- NVE is derived from the LV *galtīdan* 'to roll' (#5). Can have other meanings such as 'to roll over/toss in bed', 'to wallow/welter in the mud/in blood', '[tears] rolling/falling down', and 'to trundle'. The difference between this verb and *galt zadān* (#5) (if any) requires further research. Family (2014: 108) classifies *xordān* in this instance as expressing uncontrollable motions, involving the rotation or turning of the subject.
- Comprised of the adjective 'hunter' + the copula 'to be'.
- Comprised of the adjective 'hungry' + the copula 'to be'. Can also appear in the coding frame (1) NVE=CLT.[1] V.subj[DFLT.3SG], also known as the *Experiencer Subject Construction* (see e.g. Ghomeshi 2018: 216-217; Karimi 2018: 172-174).
- Comprised of the adjective 'sad/upset' + the copula 'to be'. Can also mean 'to be upset'.
- Comprised of the adjective 'cold' + the copula 'to be'. This coding frame is known as the *Experiencer Subject Construction* (see e.g. Ghomeshi 2018: 216-217; Karimi 2018: 172-174).

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations				Uncoded Alternations				
					Causative	Passive	-rā alternations		-rā alternations				
							-rā and be (Dative alternation)	-rā and bā (Incohesive alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	ezāfe-alternations	Other prepositional alternations		
11	FEEL PAIN	<i>dard kardān</i> ¹	1 NVE V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	FEEL	<i>ehsās kardān</i> ²	1 2+rā (LOC3) NVE V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
13	SCREAM	<i>giğ zadān</i> ³	1 NVE V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	SCREAM AT	<i>giğ zadān</i> ⁴	1 sar+e+2 NVE V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	LAUGH	<i>xandīdan</i>	1 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	LAUGH AT	<i>xandīdan</i>	1 be+2 NVE V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	be and bar
17	PLAY	<i>bāzi kardān</i> ⁵	1 NVE V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	LIVE	<i>zendegi kardān</i> ⁶	1 LOC2 NVE V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19	LEAVE	<i>tark kardān</i> ⁷	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	GO	<i>raftān</i>	1 be+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21	SING	<i>āvāz x^{av} āndān</i> ⁸	1 NVE V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22	JUMP	<i>parīdan</i>	1 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	SIT DOWN	<i>nešastān</i> ⁹	1 LOC2 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

- 1 Comprised of the noun 'pain' + the verb 'to do'. Can be interpreted as 'to ache'. The stimulus (usually a body part) is the subject (argument 1), and the experiencer is usually expressed as an pronominal enclitic attached to it.
- 2 Comprised of the noun 'feeling' + the verb 'to do'. The direct object (argument 2) is the sensation/feeling, i.e., *dard* 'pain', *xatār* 'danger', etc.
- 3 Comprised of the noun 'shreek' + the verb 'to hit'. LV can alternate with *kesīdan* 'to pull'. Family (2014: 35) classifies this LV alternation as a lexical aspectual difference related to duration.
- 4 Comprised of the noun 'shreek' + the verb 'to hit'. LV can alternate with *kesīdan* 'to pull'. Family (2014: 35) classifies this LV alternation as a lexical aspectual difference related to duration.
- 5 An ambitransitive verb. Allows Levin's (1993) *object-deletion alternation*.
- 6 Comprised of the noun 'life' + the verb 'to do'.
- 7 Comprised of the noun 'abandonment' + the verb 'to do'. Can also mean 'to abandon', 'to give up'. The verb *raftān* 'to go' (#20) can also mean 'to leave' depending on the context.
- 8 Comprised of the noun 'song' + the verb 'to read'. The LV x^{av} *āndān* lit. 'read' alone can also mean 'to sing' depending on the context.
- 9 This verb refers to the action of sitting down, not the state of being sat. Hence the Persian equivalent for the English 'to be sitting' is usually the present perfect of this verb, i.e., 'to have sat down', and the Persian present progressive is equivalent to English 'to be sitting down'. Other verbs that behave similarly include *istādan* 'to stand', x^{av} *ābidān* 'to sleep', *pušīdan* 'to wear', etc.

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations			Uncoded Alternations			
					Causative	Passive	-rā and he (Dative alternation)	-rā and hā (Inchoative alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	ezāfe alternations	Other prepositional alternations
					+	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	SIT	nešastan ¹	1 LOC 2 V.PRS.PRF.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	RUN	davidan	1 V.subj[1]	1 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
26	CLIMB	bālā rafšan ²	1 az+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
27	COUGH	sof-e kardān ³	1 NVE V.subj[1]	1 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
28	BLINK	pešk zadān ⁴	1 NVE V.subj[1]	1 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29	SHAVE	rā zadān ⁵	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	DRESS	lebās pušāndan ⁶	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	be and hā
31	WASH	sostān	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
32	EAT	xordān ⁷	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
33	HELP	kornak kardān ⁸	1 be+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
34	FOLLOW	dombāl rafšan ⁹	1 NVE=ez+2 V.subj[1]	1 NVE=ez+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	MEET	molaqāt kardān ¹⁰	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
36	HUG	bagel kardān ¹¹	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

- This verb refers to the action of sitting down, not the state of being sat. Hence the Persian equivalent for the English 'to be sitting' is usually the present perfect of this verb, i.e., 'to have sat down', and the Persian present progressive is equivalent to English 'to be sitting down'. Other verbs that behave similarly include *istādan* 'to stand', *x^{uv} ābidān* 'to sleep', *pušādan* 'to wear', etc.
- Comprised of the adverb/adjective 'upwards/high' + the verb 'to go'. Can also mean 'to go up', 'to rise (in price, temperature)'.
pušādan 'to wear', etc.
- Comprised of the noun 'cough' + the verb 'to do'.
- Comprised of the noun 'eyelid' + the verb 'to hit'.
- Comprised of the noun 'beared' + the verb 'to hit'. The LV *zadān* lit. 'hit' alone can also mean 'to shave' depending on the context. The NVE can change depending on the body part being shaved.
- The LV is a causative form of the verb *pušādan* 'to wear'. NVE may change depending on the type of clothing.
- Can also mean 'to drink'. An ambitransitive verb that allows Levin's (1993) *object-deletion alternation*. When used as LV in CP, the meaning may change to 'to collide'.
- Comprised of the noun 'help' + the verb 'to do'. LV can alternate with *dādan* 'to give'.
- Comprised of the noun 'behind/back' + the verb 'to go'. NVE is sometimes written as *dombāl* due to assimilation in pronunciation. The NVE can sometimes include the preposition *be* 'to', which can be written joined to it as in *bedombāl*.
- Comprised of the noun 'meeting' + the verb 'to do'. Used for formal meeting.
- Comprised of the noun 'hug' + the verb 'to do'. When the patient argument is a pronoun, it usually appears as a pronominal enclitic on the NVE or the LV.

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations			Uncoded Alternations		
					Causative	Passive	-rā and be (Dative alternation)	-rā alternations		Other prepositional alternations
								-rā and bā (locative alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	
37	SEARCH	<i>dombāl geshān</i> ¹	1 NVE=ez+2 V.subj[1]	1 NVE=ez+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
38	THINK	<i>fekr kardān</i> ²	1 be+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	+	be and ABOUT
39	KNOW (sb)	<i>šenāxtān</i> ³	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
40	KNOW (sth)	<i>dānestān</i>	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
41	CONSIDER	<i>dānestān</i>	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
42	LIKE	<i>soḡ āmadān</i> ⁴	(0) az+2 NVE=CLT[1] V.subj[DELT.SG]	(0) PP+2 NVE=[1] V.subj[DELT.SG]	-	-	-	-	-	-
42	LIKE/LOVE	<i>dost dāštān</i> ⁵	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
43	FEAR	<i>tarsīdān</i>	1 az+2 V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	+	-	-	-	-	-
44	FRUGHTEN	<i>tarsāndān</i> ⁶	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
45	SMELL	<i>bū kardān</i> ⁷	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
46	LOOK AT	<i>negāh kardān</i> ⁸	1 be+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
47	SEE	<i>dīdān</i> ⁹	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
48	SEE (X) AS (Y)	<i>dīdān</i>	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-

- 1 Comprised of the noun 'behind/back' + the verb 'to turn'. NVE is sometimes written as *dombāl* due to assimilation in pronunciation. The NVE can sometimes include the preposition 'to', which can be written joined to it as in *bedombāl*.
- 2 Comprised of the noun 'though' + the verb 'to do'.
- 3 Can also mean 'to recognize'.
- 4 Comprised of the adjective 'good' + the verb 'to come'. This coding frame is known as the *Experiencer Subject Construction* (see e.g., Ghomeshi 2018: 216-217; Karimi 2018: 172-174). This verb can also mean 'to be welcomed (to a place)' (fixed expression).
- 5 Comprised of the noun 'friend' + the verb 'to have'.
- 6 Causative form of the verb *tarsīdān* 'to fear' (#43).
- 7 Comprised of the noun 'smell' + the verb 'to do'. NVE is Derived from the verb *buiidān* 'to smell' (which is not used often). LV can alternate with *kesīdān* 'to pull'.
- 8 Comprised of the noun 'look' + the verb 'to do'.
- 9 Can also mean 'to meet'.

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations			Uncoded Alternations		
					Causative	Passive	-rā and be (Dative alternation)	-rā alternations		Other prepositional alternations
								-rā and bā (Inchoative alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	
49	TALK	<i>hař zadan¹</i>	1 bā+2 az+3 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 PP+3 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	+	az and ABOUT
50	ASK FOR/WANT	<i>xwāstan²</i>	1 2+rā az+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP+3 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
51	ASK FOR	<i>xwāheš kardān³</i>	1 2+rā az+3 NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP+3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	+	-
52	YELL	<i>dād zadan⁴</i>	1 V.subj[1]	1 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
53	SHOUT AT	<i>dād zadan⁴</i>	1 sar+e+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP+2 V.subj[1]	-	-	-	-	-	-
54	TELL	<i>ta arif kardān⁵</i>	1 2+rā barā+ye+3 NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP+3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	barā+ye and be
55	SAV	<i>goftan⁷</i>	1 be+2 V.subj[1] UTTS	1 2+rā PP+3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
56	NAME	<i>nāmidān⁸</i>	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
56	NAME	<i>esm gozāstan⁹</i>	1 NVE= ee+2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
57	BUILD	<i>saxtan¹⁰</i>	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
58	BREAK	<i>šekāstan¹¹</i>	1 2+rā (bā+3) V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
59	KILL	<i>košān</i>	1 2+rā (bā+3) V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-
60	BEAT	<i>koek zadan¹²</i>	1 2+rā (bā+3) V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-

- 1 Comprised of the noun 'speech' + the verb 'to hit'.
- 2 The verb meaning changes 'to want' depending on the tense and context.
- 3 Comprised of the noun 'request' + the verb 'to do'. can also mean 'you are welcome', 'please' (fixed expression).
- 4 Comprised of the noun 'yell' + the verb 'to hit'. LV can alternate with *kešidan* 'to pull'. Family (2014: 35) classifies this LV alternation as a lexical aspectual difference related to duration.
- 5 Comprised of the noun 'yell' + the verb 'to hit'. LV can alternate with *kešidan* 'to pull'. Family (2014: 35) classifies this LV alternation as a lexical aspectual difference related to duration.
- 6 Comprised of the noun 'narrative' + the verb 'to do'. can also mean 'to define', 'to praise' with different argument structure.
- 7 Usually the UTT argument (i.e., 'yes', 'no', etc.) would appear after the verb where a content clause appears.
- 8 denominal verb from the noun *nām* 'name'.
- 9 Comprised of the noun 'name' + the verb 'to put'. NVE can be replaced with the noun *nām* which also mean 'name'.
- 10 Can also replace *kardān* 'to do' for some CPrs.
- 11 Similar to English, allows Levin's (1993) *inchoative-causative alternation*.
- 12 Comprised of the noun 'beating' + the verb 'to hit'. The LV *zadan* alone can also mean 'to beat', depending on the context.

#	Core verb meaning	Verb form	Coding frame schema	Valency class	Coded Alternations				Uncoded Alternations			
					Causative	Passive	-rā alternations					
							-rā and <i>be</i> (Dative alternation)	-rā and <i>bā</i> (Inchoative alternation)	-rā and LOC (Locative alternation)	<i>ezāfe</i> alternations	Other prepositional alternations	
61	HIT	<i>zadan</i> ¹	1 2+rā (bā+3) V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
62	TOUCH	<i>dast zadan</i> ²	1 be+2 NVE V.subj[1]	1 PP-2 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
63	CUT	<i>borīdan</i> ³	1 2+rā (bā+3) V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
64	TAKE (UP)	<i>bar dāštan</i> ⁴	1 2+rā az+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
65	TAKE/RECEIVE	<i>gerfftan</i> ⁵	1 2+rā az+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
66	TAKE (X) as (V)	<i>gerffan</i>	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā 3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
67	TEAR	<i>kandān</i> ⁶	1 2+rā az+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
68	PEEL	<i>past kandān</i> ⁷	1 2+rā NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
69	HIDE	<i>panhān kardān</i> ⁸	1 2+rā az+3 NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	SHOW	<i>nemudan</i>	1 2+rā be+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
70	SHOW	<i>nesān dādan</i> ⁹	1 2+rā be+3 NVE V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
71	GIVE	<i>dādan</i>	1 2+rā be+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	SEND	<i>ferstādan</i>	1 2+rā be+3 V.subj[1]	1 2+rā PP-3 V.subj[1]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-

- 1 This LV is used predominantly in CPR (see Family 2014 for possible combinations and the semantic space map of the LV). When forming a CPR, the NVE can be the instrument, i.e., 'to beat using NVE', e.g., *čub zadan* 'stick hit'; *čomaq zadan* lit. 'club hit'. In these instances, the NVE can appear with or without the preposition *bā* 'with'.
- 2 Comprised of the noun 'hand' + the verb 'to hit'. Unless stated otherwise, usually means 'to touch with hand'.
- 3 Similar to English, allows Levin's (1993) *inchoative-causative alternation*.
- 4 Comprised of a preverb + the verb 'to have'. Can also mean 'to pick up', 'to remove'.
- 5 Can also mean 'to catch, to receive, to get'.
- 6 Can also mean 'to dig, to excavate, to pull out, to pluck'.
- 7 Comprised of the noun 'skin' + the verb 'to tear'. LV can alternate with *gerffan* 'to take'.
- 8 Comprised of the adjective 'hidden' + the verb 'to do'.
- 9 Comprised of the noun 'sign' + the verb 'to give'.

References

- Adli, Aria. 2010. Constraint cumulativity and gradience: Wh-scrambling in Persian. *Lingua* 120(9). 2259–2294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2010.01.003>.
- Ágel, Vilmos (ed.). 2006. *Dependenz und Valenz: ein internationales Handbuch der zeitgenössischen Forschung*. Berlin: Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110171525.2>.
- Allerton, D.J. 2006. Valency grammar. In Keith Brown (ed.), *Encyclopedia of language and linguistics (2nd Edition)*, 301–314. Oxford: Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-044854-2/02056-3>.
- Anderson, John M. 1971. *The Grammar of case: Towards a localistic theory*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00351940>.
- Anderson, John M. 1977. *On case grammar: Prolegomena to a theory of grammatical relations*. Croom Helm. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429460869>.
- Apresjan, Jurij D. 1969. *Èksperimental'noe issledovanie russkogo glagola [An experimental investigation into the semantics of the Russian verb]*. Moskva: Nauka.
- Assi, Seyed Mostafa. 2018. Lexicography. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 300–317. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.11>.
- Bickel, Balthasar. 2011. Grammatical relations typology. In Jae Jung Song (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Linguistic Typology*, 399–444. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199281251.013.0020>.
- Booij, Geert & Ans Van Kemenade. 2003. Preverbs: An introduction. In Geert Booij & Jaap Van Marle (eds.), *Yearbook of morphology*, 1–11. Dordrecht: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-1513-7_1.
- Bossong, Georg. 1985. *Empirische Universalienforschung: differentielle Objektmarkierung in neuiranischen Sprachen*. Tübingen: Narr.
- Bossong, Georg. 1991. Differential Object Marking in Romance and Beyond. In Dieterand Wanner & Douglas A. Kibbee (eds.), *New analyses in Romance linguistics: Selected papers from the XVIII Linguistic Symposium on Romance languages*, 143–170. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/cilt.69.14bos>.
- Bresnan, Joan, Anna Cueni, Tatiana Nikitina & R Harald Baayen. 2007. Predicting the dative alternation. In Gerlof Bouma, Irene Kramer & Joost Zwarts (eds.), *Cognitive foundations of interpretation*, 69–94. Royal Netherlands Academy of Science. <https://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-001M-0000-0013-1A32-0>.
- Browne, Wayles. 1970. More on definiteness marker: Interrogatives in Persian. *Linguistic Inquiry* 1(3). 359–363. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4177576>.
- Chafe, Wallace L. 1970. *Meaning and the structure of language*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- Comrie, Bernard. 1989. *Language universals and linguistic typology: Syntax and morphology (2nd Edition)*. Oxford: Blackwell.

- Comrie, Bernard. 1993. Argument structure. In Joachim Jacobs, Arnim von Stechow, Wolfgang Sternefeld & Theo Vennemann (eds.), *Syntax: An international handbook of contemporary research*, vol. 1, 905–914. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110095869.1.14.905>.
- Comrie, Bernard, Iren Hartmann, Martin Haspelmath, Andrej Malchukov & Søren Wichmann. 2015a. Introduction. In Andrej Malchukov & Bernard Comrie (eds.), *Valency classes in the world's languages. Vol. 1. Introducing the framework, and case studies from Africa and Eurasia*, 3–26. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-004>.
- Comrie, Bernard, Martin Haspelmath & Balthasar Bickel. 2015b. The Leipzig Glossing Rules: Conventions for interlinear morpheme-by-morpheme glosses. *Department of Linguistics of the Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology and the Department of Linguistics of the University of Leipzig* <https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/pdf/Glossing-Rules.pdf>.
- Croft, William. 2012. *Verbs: Aspect and causal structure*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199248582.001.0001>.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 1992. On the (in)dependence of syntax and pragmatics: Evidence from the postposition *-rā* in Persian. In Dieter Stein (ed.), *Cooperating with written texts: The pragmatics and comprehension of written texts*, 549–573. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110881196.549>.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 1997. Compound verbs in Persian. *Studies in the Linguistic Sciences* 27(2). 25–59. <http://hdl.handle.net/2142/11586>.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 2001. Word order typology of Iranian languages. *The Journal of Humanities* 2. 17–22. https://www.sid.ir/en/viewssid/j_pdf/99020010202.pdf.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 2006. Internal and external forces in typology: Evidence from Iranian languages. *Journal of Universal Language* 7. 29–47. <https://doi.org/10.22425/JUL.2006.7.1.29>.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 2013. *Radeshenāsi-ye zabānhā-ye Irāni [Typology of Iranian languages]*. Tehran: SAMT Organization Press.
- Dabir-Moghaddam, Mohammad. 2018. Typological approaches and dialects. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 52–88. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.3>.
- Darzi, Ali. 1996. *Word order, NP movements, and opacity conditions in Persian*: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign PhD dissertation.
- De Clerck, Bernard, Timothy Coleman & Dominique Willems (eds.). 2013. Thoughts on typologies: Different perspectives on verb classifications. *Linguistics* [special issue] 51(4). <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling-2013-0030>.
- Dixon, Robert M. W. 1991. *A New approach to English grammar, on semantic principles*. Oxford: Clarendon Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09780511611896>.

- Dixon, Robert M. W. 1994. *Ergativity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Dixon, Robert M. W. 2005. *A semantic approach to English grammar*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Dixon, Robert M. W. & Alexandra Aikhenvald. 2000. A typology of causatives: Form, syntax and meaning. In Robert M. W. Dixon & Alexandra Aikhenvald (eds.), *Changing valency: Case studies in transitivity*, 1–29. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CB09780511627750.003>.
- Drossard, Werner. 1991. Verbklassen. In Hansjakob Seiler & Waldfried Premper (eds.), *Partizipation: das sprachliche Erfassen von Sachverhalten*, 150–182. Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag.
- Faghiri, Pegah & Pollet Samvelian. 2014. Constituent ordering in Persian and the weight factor. *Empirical Issues in Syntax and Semantics* 10. 215–232. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01131198>.
- Faghiri, Pegah & Pollet Samvelian. 2015. How much is determined by the syntax? An empirical approach to the position of the direct object in Persian. In *Proceedings of the 9th Iranian conference on linguistics*, 1419–1435. Allameh Tabatabai University, Department of Linguistics, Tehran, Iran. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01220381/document>.
- Faghiri, Pegah & Pollet Samvelian. 2020. Word order preferences and the effect of phrasal length in SOV languages: Evidence from sentence production in Persian. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics* 5(1). 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.5334/gjgl.1078>.
- Faghiri, Pegah, Pollet Samvelian & Barbara Hemforth. 2014. Accessibility and word order: The case of ditransitive constructions in Persian. In Stefan Muller (ed.), *The 21th International Conference on Head-Driven Phrase Structure Grammar*, 217–237. Stanford, California: CSLI Publications. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01131190>.
- Faghiri, Pegah, Pollet Samvelian & Barbara Hemforth. 2018. Is there a canonical order in Persian ditransitive constructions? Corpus-based and experimental studies. In Agnes Korn & Andrej Malchukov (eds.), *Ditransitive constructions in a cross-linguistic perspective*, 165–185. Wiesbaden: Reichert Verlag. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01614313>.
- Family, Neiloufar. 2008. Mapping semantic spaces: A constructionist account of the “light verb” xordæn “eat” in Persian. *From polysemy to semantic change* 139–161. <https://doi.org/10.1075/slcs.106.08fam>.
- Family, Neiloufar. 2014. *Semantic spaces of Persian light verbs: A constructionist account*. Leiden: Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004274419>.
- Fillmore, Charles J. 1970. The grammar of hitting and breaking. In Roderick A. Jacobs, & Peter S. Rosenbaum (eds.), *Readings in English transformational grammar*, 120–133. Waltham, MA: Elsevier.
- Fillmore, Charles J. 1977. The case for case re-opened. In Peter Cole & Jerrold M. Sadock (eds.), *Syntax and semantics 8: Grammatical relation*, 59–81. New York: Academic Press. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004368866_005.

- Folli, Raffaella, Heidi Harley & Simin Karimi. 2005. Determinants of event type in Persian complex predicates. *Lingua* 115(10). 1365–1401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2004.06.002>.
- Ganjavi, Shadi. 2007. *Direct objects in Persian*: University of Southern California PhD dissertation.
- Ghomeshi, Jila. 1997a. Non-projecting nouns and the Ezafe construction in Persian. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 15. 729–788. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005886709040>.
- Ghomeshi, Jila. 1997b. Topics in Persian VPs. *Lingua* 133–167. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-3841\(97\)00005-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-3841(97)00005-3).
- Ghomeshi, Jila. 2018. Other approaches to syntax. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 205–225. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.8>.
- Goldberg, Adele E. 1996. Words by default: Optimizing constraints and the Persian complex predicate. In *Annual meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*, vol. 22 1, 132–146. <https://doi.org/10.3765/bls.v22i1.1360>.
- Grossman, Eitan & Alena Witzlack-Makarevich. 2019. Valency and transitivity in contact: An overview. *Journal of Language Contact* 12(1). 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1163/19552629-01201001>.
- Haig, Geoffrey. 2008. *Alignment change in Iranian languages: A construction grammar approach*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.3>.
- Haig, Geoffrey. 2011. Linker, relativizer, nominalizer, tense-particle: On the Ezāfe in West Iranian. In Foong Ha Yap, Karen Grunow-Hårst & Janick Wrona (eds.), *Nominalization in Asian languages: Diachronic and typological perspectives, vol 1: Sino-Tibetan and Iranian languages*, 363–390. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/tsl.96.13hai>.
- Haig, Geoffrey & Geoffrey Khan. 2018. Introduction. In Geoffrey Haig & Geoffrey Khan (eds.), *The languages and linguistics of Western Asia: An areal perspective*, 1–29. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110421682-001>.
- Haig, Geoffrey & Mohammad Rasekh-Mahand. 2019. Post-predicate elements in Iranian and neighbouring languages: Inheritance, contact, and information structure. Position Paper. https://www.uni-bamberg.de/fileadmin/aspra/05_Events/2019_Post-predicate_elements_in_Iranian/2019_post-predicate_iranian_position_paper_haig_rasekhmahand2019.pdf.
- Hartmann, Iren, Martin Haspelmath & Bradley Taylor (eds.). 2013. *Valency Patterns Leipzig (Database)*. Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology. <http://valpal.info>.
- Haspelmath, Martin. 2011. On S, A, P, T, and R as comparative concepts for alignment typology. *Linguistic Typology* 15. 535–567.
- Haspelmath, Martin. 2014. Arguments and adjuncts as language-particular syntactic categories and as comparative concepts. *Linguistic Discovery* 12(2). 3–11.

- Haspelmath, Martin. 2015. Transitivity prominence. In Andrej Malchukov & Bernard Comrie (eds.), *Valency classes in the world's languages. Vol. 1. Introducing the framework, and case studies from Africa and Eurasia*, 131–147. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-008>.
- Haspelmath, Martin & Iren Hartmann. 2015. Comparing verbal valency across languages. In Andrej Malchukov & Bernard Comrie (eds.), *Valency classes in the world's languages. Vol. 1. Introducing the framework, and case studies from Africa and Eurasia*, 41–71. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-006>.
- Helbig, Gerhard & Wolfgang Schenkel. 1969. *Wörterbuch zur Valenz und Distribution deutscher Verben*. Leipzig: Bibliographisches Institut.
- Hellan, Lars, Michela Cennamo & Andrej Malchukov. 2017. Introduction. Issues in contrastive valency studies. In Lars Hellan, Michela Cennamo & Andrej Malchukov (eds.), *Contrastive studies in verbal valency*, 1–24. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/la.237>.
- Hopper, Paul J. & Sandra A. Thompson. 1980. Transitivity in grammar and discourse. *language* 56. 251–299.
- Jackendoff, Ray. 1976. Toward an explanatory semantic representation. *Linguistic inquiry* 7(1). 89–150. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4177913>.
- Jasbi, Masoud. 2020. The meaning of the Persian object marker *râ*: What it is not, and what it (probably) is. In K. Larson Richard, Sedigheh Moradi & Vida Samiian (eds.), *Advances in Iranian linguistics*, 119–135. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/cilt.351.07jas>.
- Kahnemuyipour, Arsalan. 2014. Revisiting the Persian *Ezafe* construction: A roll-up movement analysis. *Lingua* 150. 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2014.07.012>.
- Karimi, Simin. 1989. *Aspects of Persian syntax, specificity, and the theory of grammar*: University of Washington PhD dissertation.
- Karimi, Simin. 1990. Obliqueness, specificity, and discourse functions: *Râ* in Persian. *Linguistic Analysis* 20(3-4). 139–191.
- Karimi, Simin. 1996. Case and specificity: Persian *râ* revisited. *Linguistic Analysis* 26. 174–194.
- Karimi, Simin. 1999. Is scrambling as strange as we think it is. *MIT working papers in Linguistics* 33. 159–190. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.232.9972&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.
- Karimi, Simin. 2003. On object positions, specificity, and scrambling in Persian. In Simin Karimi (ed.), *Word order and scrambling*, 91–124. Oxford: Blackwell Malden. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470758403.ch5>.
- Karimi, Simin. 2008. *A minimalist approach to scrambling: Evidence from Persian*. De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110199796>.
- Karimi, Simin. 2018. Generative approaches to syntax. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 161–204. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.7>.

- Karimi, Simin & Michael Brame. 2012. A Generalization concerning the Ezafe construction in Persian. *Linguistic Analysis* 38. 111–143.
- Karimi, Simin & Ryan Walter Smith. 2020. another look at Persian rā. In K. Larson Richard, Sedigheh Moradi & Vida Samiian (eds.), *Advances in Iranian linguistics*, 155–172. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/cilt.351.09kar>.
- Karimi-Doostan, Gholamhossein. 1997. *Light verb constructions in Persian*: University of Essex PhD dissertation. <http://lear.unive.it/jspui/handle/11707/3973>.
- Karimi-Doostan, Gholamhossein. 2005. Light verbs and structural case. *Lingua* 115(12). 1737–1756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2004.08.002>.
- Karimi-Doostan, Gholamhossein. 2011. Separability of light verb constructions in Persian. *Studia Linguistica* 65(1). 70–95. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9582.2011.01178.x>.
- Kratochvíl, František, Alexander R. Coupe & Randy J. LaPolla (eds.). 2011. Studies in transitivity: Insights from language documentation. *Studies in Language* [special issue] 35(3). <https://doi.org/10.1075/sl.35.3>.
- Larson, Richard & Vida Samiian. 2020. The Ezafe construction revisited. In Richard Larson, Sedigheh Moradi & Vida Samiian (eds.), *Advances in Iranian Linguistics*, 173–236. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Larson, Richard & Hiroko Yamakido. 2008. Ezafe and the deep position of nominal modifiers. In Louise McNally & Chris Kennedy (eds.), *Adjectives and adverbs: Syntax, semantics and discourse*, 43–70. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lazard, Gilbert. 1982. Le morpheme rā en Persan et les relations actanciennes. *Bulletin de la Société de Linguistique de Paris* 73(1). 177–208.
- Lazard, Gilbert. 1992. *A grammar of contemporary Persian*. Costa Mesa, CA: Mazda Publishers.
- Lazard, Gilbert. 1994. Le rā Persan et le ba chinois. *Cahiers de linguistique Asie orientale* 23(1). 169–176.
- Lazard, Gilbert. 1998. *Actancy*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110808100>.
- Lehmann, Christian. 1991. Predicate classes and participation. In Hansjakob Seiler & Waldfried Premper (eds.), *Partizipation: das sprachliche Erfassen von Sachverhalten*, 183–239. Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag.
- Levin, Beth. 1993. *English verb classes and alternations: A preliminary investigation*. University of Chicago Press.
- Levin, Beth & Malka Hovav Rappaport. 2005. *Argument realization*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mahmoodi-Bakhtiari, Behrooz. 2018. Morphology. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 273–300. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.10>.

- Mahootian, Shahrzad. 1997. *Persian*. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203192887>.
- Malchukov, Andrej. 2005. Case pattern splits, verb types and construction competition. In Mengistu Amberber & Helen de Hoop (eds.), *Competition and variation in natural languages*, 73–117. Amsterdam: Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-008044651-6/50006-9>.
- Malchukov, Andrej. 2006. Transitivity parameters and transitivity alternations: Constraining covariation. In Leonid Kulikov, Andrej Malchukov & Peter de Swart (eds.), *Case, valency and transitivity*, 329–357. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/slcs.77.21mal>.
- Malchukov, Andrej. 2016. “Ambivalent voice”: Markedness effects in valency change. In Taro Kageyama & Wesley M. Jacobsen (eds.), *Transitivity and valency alternations: Studies on Japanese and beyond*, 389–422. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110477153-014>.
- Malchukov, Andrej & Bernard Comrie (eds.). 2015a. *Valency classes in the world’s languages. Vol. 1. Introducing the framework, and case studies from Africa and Eurasia*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-004>.
- Malchukov, Andrej & Bernard Comrie (eds.). 2015b. *Valency classes in the world’s languages. Vol. 2. Case Studies from Austronesia, the Pacific, the Americas, and Theoretical Outlook*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-004>.
- Malchukov, Andrej, Martin Haspelmath & Bernard Comrie (eds.). 2010. *Studies in ditransitive constructions: A comparative handbook*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110220377>.
- Malchukov, Andrej & Leipzig Valency Classes Project team. 2015. Leipzig questionnaire on valency classes. In Andrej Malchukov & Bernard Comrie (eds.), *Valency classes in the world’s languages. Vol. 1. Introducing the framework, and case studies from Africa and Eurasia*, 27–40. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110338812-005>.
- Megerdooomian, Karine. 2001. Event structure and complex predicates in Persian. *Canadian Journal of Linguistics/Revue canadienne de linguistique* 46(1-2). 97–125. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0008413100017953>.
- Megerdooomian, Karine. 2012. The status of the nominal in Persian complex predicates. *Natural Language & Linguistic Theory* 30(1). 179–216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11049-011-9146-0>.
- Næss, Åshild. 2007. *Prototypical transitivity*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Nunberg, Geoffrey, Ivan A Sag & Thomas Wasow. 1994. Idioms. *Language* 70(3). 491–538. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.1994.0007>.
- Paul, Ludwig. 2018. Persian. In Geoffrey Haig & Geoffrey Khan (eds.), *The languages and linguistics of Western Asia: An areal perspective*, 569–624. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110421682-017>.
- Perry, John R. 2007. Persian morphology. *Morphologies of Asia and Africa* 2. 975–1019. <https://www.academia.edu/42846867>.

- Perry, John Richard. 2002. Arabic language. v. Arabic elements in Persian. In *Encyclopaedia Iranica*, Online edition. <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/arabic-v>. (Accessed: 15.12.2022).
- Rasekh-Mahand, Mohammad. 2003. *Qalb-e nahvi dar zabān-e Fārsi [Scrambling in Persian]*: Allameh Tabatabaei University PhD dissertation.
- Rasooli, Mohammad Sadegh, Manouchehr Kouhestani & Amirsaeid Moloodi. 2013. Development of a Persian syntactic dependency treebank. In *Proceedings of the conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human language technologies*, 306–314. Atlanta, Georgia, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/N13-1031.pdf>.
- Rasooli, Mohammad Sadegh, Amirsaeid Moloodi, Manouchehr Kouhestani & Behrouz Minaei-Bidgoli. 2011. A syntactic valency lexicon for Persian verbs: The first steps towards Persian dependency treebank. In *5th Language and Technology Conference (LTC): Human language technologies as a challenge for computer science and linguistics*, 227–231. Poznań, Poland: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230612993>.
- Samiian, Vida. 1983. *Structure of phrasal categories in Persian: An X-bar analysis*: UCLA PhD dissertation.
- Samiian, Vida. 1994. The Ezafe Construction: Some implications for the theory of X-bar syntax. In Mehdi Marashi (ed.), *Persian studies in North America*, 17–41. Bethesda: Iranbooks.
- Samvelian, Pollet. 2007. A phrasal affix analysis of the Persian Ezafe. *Journal of Linguistics* 43. 605–645. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022226707004781>.
- Samvelian, Pollet. 2008. The Ezafe as a head-marking inflectional affix: Evidence from Persian and Kurmanji Kurdish. In Simin Karimi, Vida Samiian & Donald Stilo (eds.), *Aspects of Iranian linguistics*, 339–361. Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-00673182>.
- Samvelian, Pollet. 2012. *Grammaire des prédicats complexes: Les constructions nom-verbe*. Paris: Lavoisier.
- Samvelian, Pollet. 2018. Specific features of Persian syntax: The Ezafe Construction, Differential Object Marking and Complex Predicates. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 226–269. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.9>.
- Samvelian, Pollet & Pegah Faghiri. 2013a. Introducing PersPred, a Syntactic and Semantic Database for Persian complex predicates. In *Proceedings of the 9th Workshop on multi-word expressions*, 11–20. Atlanta, Georgia, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/W13-1002>.
- Samvelian, Pollet & Pegah Faghiri. 2013b. Re-thinking compositionality in Persian complex predicates. In *Annual meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*, vol. 39 1, 212–226. <https://doi.org/10.3765/bls.v39i1.3882>.
- Samvelian, Pollet & Pegah Faghiri. 2014. Persian complex predicates: How compositional are they? *Semantics-Syntax Interface* 1(1). 43–74. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01136825>.

- Samvelian, Pollet, Pegah Faghiri & Sarra El Ayari. 2014. Extending the coverage of a MWE database for Persian CPs exploiting valency alternations. In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'14)*, 4023–4026. Reykjavik, Iceland: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2014/pdf/883_Paper.pdf.
- Sedigheh, Moradi. 2020. Advances in Iranian linguistics. In K. Larson Richard, Sedigheh Moradi & Vida Samiian (eds.), *Advances in iranian linguistics*, 1–13. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/cilt.351.01mor>.
- Sedighi, Anousha. 2009. Do psychological constructions in Persian involve complex predicates? *Rice Working Papers in Linguistics* 1. 65–78. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:55314962>.
- Sedighi, Anousha & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi. 2018. Introduction. In Anousha Sedighi & Pouneh Shabani-Jadidi (eds.), *The Oxford handbook of Persian linguistics*, 1–6. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198736745.013.1>.
- Seržant, Ilja A. & Alenaa Witzlack-Makarevich. 2018. Differential argument marking: Patterns of variation. In Ilja A. Seržant & Alena Witzlack-Makarevich (eds.), *Argument selectors: A new perspective on grammatical relations*, 1–40. Berlin: Language Science Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1219168>.
- Stilo, Donald. 2004. Coordination in three Western Iranian languages: Vafsi, Persian and Gilaki. In Martin Haspelmath (ed.), *Coordinating constructions*, 269–330. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/tsl.58.16sti>.
- Stilo, Donald. 2005. Iranian as buffer zone between the universal typologies of Turkic and Semitic. In Éva Ágnes Csató, Bo Isaksson & Carina Jahani (eds.), *Linguistic convergence and areal diffusion: Case studies from Iranian, Semitic, and Turkic*, 35–64. London: Routledge Curzon. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203327715>.
- Stilo, Donald. 2006. Circumpositions as an areal response: The case study of the Iranian zone. In Lars Johanson & Christiane Bulut (eds.), *Turkic–Iranian contact areas: Historical and linguistic aspects*, 310–333. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz. <https://www.academia.edu/62641385>.
- Stilo, Donald. 2012. Intersection zones, overlapping isoglosses, and ‘fade-out/fade-in’ phenomena in Central Iran. In Behrad Aghaei & M.R. Ghanoonparvar (eds.), *Iranian languages and culture: Essays in honor of Gernot Ludwig Windfuhr*, 3–33. Costa Mesa: Mazda Publishers.
- Stilo, Donald. 2015. An introduction to the Atlas of the Araxes-Iran Linguistic Area. In Bernard Comrie & Lucía Golluscio (eds.), *Language Contact and Documentation / Contacto lingüístico y documentación*, 343–356. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110317473.343>.
- Sulayman, Hayyim. 1962. *New Persian-English dictionary, complete and modern*. Teheran: Librairie-imprimerie Bérroukhim. <https://dsal.uchicago.edu/dictionaries/hayyim/>.
- Tabibzadeh, Omid. 2006. *Zarfīyat-e fel va sāxthā-ye bonyādin jomle dar Fārsi-ye emruz: Pežuheši bar asās-e nazriye-ye dastur-e vābestegi [Verb valency and sentence base structures in Modern Persian: Dependency-based approach]*. Tehran: Markaz.

- Tesnière, Lucien. 1959. *Éléments de syntaxe structurale*. Paris: Klincksieck.
- Tsunoda, Tasaku. 1981. Split case-marking in verb types and tense/aspect/mood. *Linguistic* 19. 389–438.
- Tsunoda, Tasaku. 1985. Remarks on transitivity. *Journal of Linguistic* 21. 385–396.
- Windfuhr, Gernot L. 1979. *Persian grammar: History and state of its study*. The Hague: Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110800425>.
- Windfuhr, Gernot L. & Carina Jahani. 2018. Persian. In Bernard Comrie (ed.), *The world's major languages (3rd Edition)*, 455–469. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315644936>.
- Windfuhr, Gernot L. & John R. Perry. 2009. Persian and Tajik. In Gernot L. Windfuhr (ed.), *The Iranian languages*, 416–544. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203641736>.
- Witzlack-Makarevich, Alena. 2011. *Typological variation in grammatical relations*: University of Leipzig PhD dissertation.
- Witzlack-Makarevich, Alena. 2019. Argument selectors: A new perspective on grammatical relations. An introduction. In Alena Witzlack-Makarevich & Balthasar Bickel (eds.), *Argument selectors: A new perspective on grammatical relations*, 1–38. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/tsl.123.01wit>.
- Zúñiga, Fernando & Seppo Kittilä. 2019. *Grammatical voice*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316671399>.